

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D5.3 Engagement activities reporting v1

WP5 - Engagement, change
management and sustainability

Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

The deliverable 5.3. *Engagement activities reporting v1* includes information about three different tasks: T5.2 *Engaging with the innovation ecosystems*, T5.3 *Raising awareness and engagement activities* and T6.2 *Intra-institutional internal communication*. These tasks include the implementation of the dedicated engagement activities organised by the CALIPER seven RPOs and two RFOs, aimed at creating a favourable environment for the implementation and institutionalisation of their tailored Gender Equality Plans. This deliverable provides information about the four main engagement activities that each RPO and RFO has implemented in the past months namely 1. Online raising awareness session (1st round) (T5.3), 2. Internal workshop with GEP working group (T5.3) 3. Public online event (T6.2) and the 4. Women and Innovation (win) event (T5.2). Overall, these activities aim to disseminate the partners' GEPs and increase the engagement with their GEP actions of both internal and external stakeholders. This first version of the report contains details about the events, focusing on their impact and outreach.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

A GEP should be actively communicated both internally and externally to increase awareness and engagement to the actions foreseen. Taking into consideration this fact, several communication and engagement actions are foreseen within the CALIPER's lifetime for ensuring internal and external commitment of key stakeholders that will in turn facilitate the implementation and the sustainability of the tailored GEP for each CALIPER partner.

This deliverable, D5.3, which is the first version of the engagement activities reporting, aims to present those internal and external engagement activities/sessions organised by each CALIPER RPO/RFO up until now and which were foreseen under tasks:

- T5.2 Engaging with the innovation ecosystems,
- T5.3 Raising awareness and engagement activities and
- T6.2 Intra-institutional internal communication.

In particular, the activities organised per CALIPER partners were:

1. The internal workshop(s) with GEPs Working Groups for discussing further the results of T1.3 and T1.4 to understand the potentials and barriers in each participating country and within the identified framework conditions and hence to exploit its own innovation environments by building strategic collaboration and therefore enhancing gender equality (Part of T5.3)
2. The first round of the online raising awareness sessions for raising awareness among internal staff and giving additional content to support the GEP Working Groups in raising internal awareness and increase engagement throughout the different steps of the structural change process (Part of T5.3)
3. A Public online event for presenting the partners GEP and for engaging external stakeholders from the local innovation ecosystems with the GEP's activities (Part of T6.2)
4. The Women in Innovation – Win event having a double fold aim: 1. To highlight the and value women's led innovations 2. To work as a means of raising awareness and attracting more girls in STEM research (part of T5.2)

These 4 different activities were organised as a standalone session or some of them merged into one session by the partners depending on their objectives. In addition, the public online events, as part of T6.2, were not supposed to be reported in this deliverable, but as it is evident from the reports below some of the partners merged this session with the online awareness raising session, in order to attract more participants and bring the internal and external relevant stakeholders together for increasing the legitimacy of the presented actions of the GEP.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured in five chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the present deliverable along with its linkages with other WPs and Tasks. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the internal and external engagement activities that each RPO and RFO had to organise within the context of T5.2, T5.3 and T6.3 describing their purpose and objectives. Chapter 3 presents the implemented activities per RPO/RFO. Last, chapter 4 includes a few final remarks of the deliverable and provides some more information about the upcoming engagement activities.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is part of Task 5.3: *Raising awareness and engagement activities* of WP5 *Engagement, change management and sustainability*, aiming at presenting the results of the engagement activities, organised by the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs to disseminate their GEP internally and externally. This task is linked to T5.2. *Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIPER Win Events*. T5.3 also contributes to WP6 *Dissemination and communication*, and more specifically to T6.2 *Intra-institutional internal communication*, and T6.3 *External communication and multiplying effect*. These tasks are related due to the communication and dissemination activities they include, as well as the fact that the activities reported in this deliverable belong to three different tasks: T5.2, T5.3, and T6.2. The D5.3 is also interlinked with T1.3. *Methods and good practices on engendering research- innovation ecosystems* T1.4. *Analysis of external framework conditions and innovation ecosystems from a gender perspective GEPs* and T2.2. *The organisation of Multi Stakeholder dialogues* since the reported activities were based on information gathered for the purposes of these tasks.

2 Overview and objectives of the internal and external engagement activities

This chapter gives a brief overview of the scope of each internal and external engagement activity that each partners had to organised up until now. These activities are:

1. The internal workshop(s) with GEPs Working Groups (Part of T5.3)
2. The first round of the online raising awareness sessions (Part of T5.3)
3. The Public online event for presenting the partners GEP and for engaging external stakeholders from the local innovation ecosystems with the GEP's activities (Part of T6.2)
4. The Women in Innovation – Win event (part of T5.2)

Overall, those activities aim at having **inward impact** by promoting structural changes for gender equality internally via engaging internal stakeholders for facilitating the institutionalization of your GEP activities and **outward impact by** expanding and promote the project results in the local innovation ecosystem via the involvement of the CALIPER R&I local Hubs

2.1 Internal workshop with GEP working groups

During the past months the CALIPER RPO/RFOs have developed and now implementing a tailored GEP. Throughout this process a GEP working group created by each RPO/RFO consisted of staff members at different managerial levels and specialisations (ie Human Resources, Research Support, and Institutional Communication etc). The mission of these group is to implement the individual internal engagement and change management strategy for each RPO/ RFO towards gender equality.

Within the *Task 5.3: Raising awareness and engagement activities*, each GEP implementing partner had to organise an internal workshop with their respective GEPs Working Group aimed at discussing further the results of T1.3 Methods and good practices on engendering *research and innovation ecosystems* and T1.4 *Analysis of external framework conditions and innovation ecosystems from a gender perspective*, to understand the potentials and barriers in each participating country and within the identified framework conditions and hence to exploit its own innovation environments by building strategic collaboration and therefore enhancing gender equality (Part of T5.3)

2.2 Online awareness session

Within the *Task 5.3: Raising awareness and engagement activities* each GEP implementing partner must organise three rounds of online raising awareness sessions aiming at providing additional content to support the GEP Working Groups in raising internal awareness, increase engagement throughout the different steps of the structural change process and facilitate the change of the institutional culture based on gender equality, inclusion, and diversity. Three rounds of online raising awareness sessions are foreseen to be implemented in each RPO and RFO for going more in depth on facts, arguments, tools, and strategies to address each one of the three ERA objectives on gender equality, on which the CALIPER inclusive GEPs are contributing. The present deliverable focused on the first round of the online awareness sessions.

2.3 Public online event

With the CALIPER project, each RPO/ RFO created their CALIPER Research & Innovation (R&I) Hubs involving key external stakeholders from research and academia, government, business, and civil society and engaged throughout the project's lifetime.

In particular, within the context of *T6.2 Intra-institutional internal communication* each participating RPO/RFO had to organise one public info session to present externally (including the members of their (R&I) Hub) their GEP and respective insight of it. The public online events, aimed at engaging external target audience. The public online events had to be open to the public, where national stakeholders such as other RPOs/RFOs, as well as stakeholders from R&I Hubs could participate. The goal of this type of event, is to communicate the achievements of the RPOs/RFOs to the local and national stakeholders and attract more institutions and organisations to collaborate with them towards institutional change.

As already mentioned in chapter 1, the public online events, were not supposed to be reported in this deliverable, but some of the partners merged this session with the online awareness raising session, in order to attract more participants and bring the internal and external relevant stakeholders together for increasing the legitimacy of the presented actions of the GEP. Thus the respective activity for all partners is presented here.

2.4 Women in Innovation – Win event

The project acknowledging that gender stereotypes also exist in the business sector and that more women in STEM is needed and for tackling these issues within the context of *T5.2 Engaging with the innovation ecosystems*, each GEP implementing partner had to organise an event (Win event). In particular, the WIN event had a double fold aim: on one side it highlighted and value women's led innovations presenting startups and spin offs and examples of gender sensitive product development/design; on the other hand, it works as a means of raising awareness and attracting more girls to STEM research.

The following chapter presents the main results for each one of these events as they have been organised by each caliper RPO and RFO.

3 Reports of the events

This chapter presents the reports of the engagement activities per RPO/RFO. There are nine sub sections, one per partner, containing the respective subsections with more details about each of the event organised by the CALIPER partners. It is worth to mention that many partners decided to hold combined events, to attract more participants and bring the internal and external target audience together. In this case the reports are joint.

3.1 Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing – University of Zagreb (UZG – FER)

3.1.1 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

The workshop was organised to present to the GEP Working group accomplishments of the previous period and plans for the forthcoming period. The session was held on site on October 15th, 2021, at UZG-FER from 12:00 – 13:30.

Agenda

Adoptation of Gender Equality Plan
Implementation of GEP for academic year 2021/2022

Table 1 UZG-FER internal workshop agenda

Participants

The workshop was led by the principal researcher of CALIPER – Anamari Nakić. The present members of the working group were the following

N.	Female/male	Position
1.	M	Head of Department of Electronic Systems and Information Processing / Research Group Lead
2.	F	Head of Committee for Doctoral Studies / Research Group Lead
3.	F	CALIPER project team member
4.	M	Vice Dean / Research Group Lead
5.	F	CALIPER project Principal Researcher

Table 2 Audience breakdown of the internal workshop

Minutes

The workshop was organised after the Faculty Council, on 15 September 2021, were the Gender Equality Plan was officially adopted for the period 2021–2025 with the following objectives:

- To inform the Working group about the process of adaptation of the GEP by the Dean and the Faculty Council
- To present and discuss GEP activities in the forthcoming period
- To engage the participants in the application of the GEP across all organisational levels

The workshop started with an overview of the activities that have already been done towards the official adoption of GEP by the Faculty Council. After the brief discussion, the GEP actions which were planned to be implemented in the academic year 2021/2022 were presented.

Planned actions of the GEP for 2021/2022

3.2 Reporting on the status of gender equality

-
- 3.3 Pilot programme for empowerment of female researchers
-
- 4.1 Establishment of a dedicated digital communication channel
-
- 5.1 Integration of the gender dimension in teaching
-
- 5.4 Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer
-
- 6.2 Attracting new female students to the Faculty
-

Table 3 Planned actions of the GEP for 2021/2022

Each action was discussed in detail: timeline, activities, involved of internal and external stakeholders and possible synergies. The next workshop took place in may 17th 2022 in order to follow the implementation of the mentioned actions.

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 1 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the UZG-FER events

3.1.2 Online awareness session & Public online event

Introduction

The session was organised to announce the launch of the first Gender Equality Plan of the Faculty of electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb to the internal and external stakeholders. The session was held on site on October 20, 2021, at UZG-FER from 11:00 - 13:30.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Responsible and duration
11:00 – 11:10	Opening and welcome speech	Dean Gordan Gledec
11:10 – 11:40	Presentation of Gender Equality Plan of UZG-FER	Prof. Anamari Nakić, CALIPER project lead researcher
11:40 – 12:55	Discussion	Moderator A. Nakić
12:55 – 13:00	Conclusion	Dean Gordan Gledec

Table 4 Agenda of the internal workshop

Participants

In total 50 persons participated (37F and 13M). 30 participants are employees of UZG-FER occupying various positions, and 20 participants are external stakeholders employed at the following organisations:

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Type of external stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia & universities (5)	Faculty of Philosophy, University of Rijeka, Faculty of Organisation and Informatics, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Algebra, University of Applied Sciences Zagreb
Industry (3)	STEMI, Ericsson Nikola Tesla, CROZ
Ministries/Government (3)	Central State Office for the Development of Digital Society of Republic of Croatia, Gender Equality Office of Republic of Croatia, Ministry of Science and Education
Public sector (3)	XV. Gymnasium, Technical Museum Nikola Tesla, Agency for Mobility and EU Programs
Civil society organisations (1)	Women in Engineering Croatia

Table 5 Audience from the R&I Hub

Minutes

The objectives of the online awareness session were:

- Stress the need for gender equality and gender mainstreaming
- Explain why equality of opportunity is interesting and necessary for public bodies, research organisations, universities, and faculties.
- Engage all sessions' participants in application of GEPs across all organisational levels in institutions.
- Present inspirational good practices from other research institutions or even companies which introduced GEPs

The main presentation included overview of the current European context (new eligibility criteria for institutions participating in Horizon Europe, identified challenges of the European Research Area). After that, a brief overview of the results of internal analysis of the current state of gender equality at UZG-FER was described in order to motivate the measures they adopted for execution. Then, due to limited time, 6 of the activities that are planned to be executed in this academic year, were described, along with the work undertaken by the GEP working group. The presentation finished with an overview of the collaborations of UZG – FER with the external stakeholders, in the context of the R&I Hub. This was an introduction to a lively discussion that followed.

The participants commented findings of the analysis and well as their impression of the GEP of UZG-FER. Several speakers emphasised the importance of internal analysis before adopting activities. Overall, the feedback was very positive, and they reaffirmed the strong connections with stakeholders.

Supporting material

Presentation slides

Figure 2 FER public event and the awareness raising session slides

Photos

Figure 3 FER public event and the awareness raising session photos

3.1.3 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

On April 28 and 30, 2022, a two-day **FER-WIN** was held at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (FER). As part of the event, they organised a panel discussion on women's experiences in innovation, along with the presentation of the publication on the first female researchers at FER and the programming workshops for primary school students. About 30 FER students, employees and alumni participated in the organisation and implementation, and various activities attracted over 200 visitors aged 5 to 90+. The activities were carried out with the aim of raising the visibility of female students, alumni, employees, and researchers, as part of the implementation of the FER Gender Equality Plan.

Agenda

Panel discussion

April 28, 2022 (Day1)

Time	Item
9:30 – 10:00	Arrival
10:00 – 11:00	Panel discussion: Women in Innovation Dr. Petra Maždin Dr. Ivana Nižetić Kosović Dr. Ivana Stupar Moderator: dr. Anamari Nakić
11:00 – 11:30	Q & A
11:30 – 12:00	Coffee break
12:00 – 13:00	Book presentation: First female scientists at FER Moderator: Branka Marijanović Assoc. prof. Mihaela Vranić Prof. Jelka Petrak Prof. Maja Matijašević Prof. Emer. Branka Zovko-Cihlar
13:00 – 14:00	Mingle & Networking, Coffee break

Table 6 FER – WIN agenda (Day 1)

Programming workshop

April 30, 2022 (Day 2)

The programming workshop for elementary school students was organised in three timeslots. They were divided into three parts, depending on the age of participants: Scratch, LEGO Mindstorms EV3, Croduino.

10:00 – 11:30	Three workshops in parallel sessions: Croduino, Lego, Scratch
11:30 – 12:00	Fun room: exploring robotics through playing
12:00 – 13:30	Three workshops in parallel sessions: Croduino, Lego, Scratch
13:30 – 14:00	Fun room: exploring robotics through playing
14:00 – 15:30	Three workshops in parallel sessions: Croduino, Lego, Scratch
15:30 – 16:00	Fun room: exploring robotics through playing

Table 7 FER – WIN agenda (Day 2)

Participants

Panel discussion

For the sessions of the first day, the target audience was young female doctoral students employed at FER, as well as employees and external stakeholders that participated in the various previous activities of the

CALIPER project. In total, 15 people from 8 external stakeholders participated in the event. In addition, 30 employees of FER participated: 4 members of the project team that organised the dialogue, vice dean for education, 1 member of the CALIPER Working group of CALIPER, and 24 professors and employees of FER. In total there was 45 participants and organisers: 35 women and 10 men.

Stakeholder	Type
Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb (1 person)	Academia
Faculty of Medicine, University of Zagreb (1 person)	Academia
Rectorate, University of Zagreb (2 persons)	Academia
Faculty of Philosophy, University of Zagreb (1 person)	Academia
Lemax (1 person)	Industry
Ericsson Nikola Tesla (3 persons)	Industry
Končar Institut za elektrotehniku (5 persons)	Industry
Q Agency (1 person)	Industry

Table 8 FER-WIN Participants' stakeholder type

Programming workshop

For the programming workshop on the second day, April 30, 2022, UZG-FER had 50 places available in each of the three planned timeslots, and all of them were full. In total 158 students at elementary schools participated. The workshops were lead and organised by 20 female students, employees and alumni of FER.

Grade	Number of participants
1 st grade (age 6)	24 (14M / 10F)
2 nd grade	39 (22M / 17F)
3 rd grade	25 (14M / 11F)
4 th grade	19 (8M / 11F)
5 th grade	15 (6M / 9F)
6 th grade	6 (5M / 1F)
7 th grade	17 (12M / 5F)
8 th grade	13 (13M / 0F)

Table 9 FER-WIN Student participants' age groups

Minutes

In the panel discussion during the first day, the main goal was to present women in innovation, and researchers that obtained their PhD degree at FER and now work in the R&D industry. In the conversation, they described their experiences from the doctoral study, lifelong motivation for research work and ongoing cooperation with researchers from FER.

During the second half of the panel discussion, the presentation of a book about the first female researchers of FER was presented. This session was moderated by Branka Marijanović, the editor of the publication and the and head of the Central Library of FER. The publication provides a brief overview of the socio-historical context of women's inclusion in the scientific and educational system and presents the first seven scientists in the field of electrical engineering who worked at the faculty until 1970. These are prof. Višnja Henč-Bartolić, M.Sc. Marica Jurišić-Zec, prof. Vesna Kos, prof. Jasna Šimunić-Hrvoić, M.Sc. sc. Mirjana Urbiha-Feuerbach, M.Sc. sc. Kalma Zimmermann-Pavčević and prof. Branka Zovko-Cihlar.

They discussed the participation and contribution of women in research and teaching conducted at FER from their respective perspectives. The year 1919 is the beginning of teaching and studying electrical engineering in Croatia. From the academic year 1928/1929 until 1970/1971, 3188 persons graduated in the field of electrical engineering, of which 3040 were men (95.4%) and 148 were women (4.6%). In the same period,

110 men (90.2%) and 12 women (9.8%) received their master's degrees, and 56 men (96.5%) and two women (3.5%) received their doctorates.

The publication presents seven outstanding women who worked at FER in the field of electrical engineering until 1970, at a time when the technical profession was considered more suitable for men. From the historical context described in the text anyone can easily see what challenges they faced in their professional and scientific path and what factors influenced their empowerment.

On the other hand, the figures from 2020 show that in recent years, female students make up one fifth of the student population at all levels of study at FER, and the percentage of women employed at FER in research and scientific-teaching jobs shows an upward trend.

The main organiser of the programming workshop was Ana Šelek, a PhD student working at FER. The programming workshop for elementary school students was divided into three parts, depending on the age of participants: Scratch, LEGO Mindstorms EV3 and Croduino. The workshops covered various topics: climate change, space exploration and traffic. In addition, they organised a "fun room" where students could have fun and get acquainted with robots STEMI, Sphero, Codey Rocky, Lego robots, mini Tesla transformer, applications that use augmented reality and make luminous greeting cards. It was organised in collaboration with [Stemalica](#), NGO for STEM education of children and [ŠUZA](#), official program of FER for science popularisation.

Overall, the organisers and participants were satisfied with the event, which also attracted considerable attention. Most of the organisers express hope that this event will become annual manifestation of FER.

Supporting material

Publications

Figure 4 Women in Innovation – [First female researchers at FER](#)

Link to journal article about CALIPER and programming workshops for students in [Žene i mediji](#)

Recording of the session

[FER-WIN recordings](#)

Photos

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 5 FER – WIN photos

Figure 6 FER – WIN kids’ activity

3.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG)

3.2.1 Online awareness session & public online event

Introduction

The online awareness session and public online event were organised together on 06.10.2021. During the session SRNSFG team presented the GEP to internal and external stakeholders and announced its launch.

Besides that, during the session external stakeholders delivered presentations about the importance of raising awareness on gender inequalities in STEM and shared inspirational good practices from their research institutions. The event started at 16:00 and lasted 2 hours.

Agenda

15:45 - 16:00	Registration	Technical check
16:00 – 16:15	Evaluation Review, ERA connection, Presentation of GEP (particular actions, dates);	Prof. Nino Gachechiladze (SRNSFG);
16:15 – 16:30	Institutional Communication (particular actions with dates), collaboration actions and planned activities;	Dr. Rusudan Jobava (SRNSFG);
16:30 – 16:45	Changes in scientific direction – collaboration activities (with dates)	Lana Davituliani (SRNSFG);
16:45 – 17:00	Gender related problems in academic environment and existing regulations	Prof. Tamar Gurchiani (Ilia State University);
17:00 – 17:15	Sharing Best practice	Prof. Nani Matcharashvili (GIPA);
17:15 – 17:25	Summary	

Table 10 SRNSFG online awareness session and public event agenda

Participants

The session was attended by 16 participants, (15 females, and 1 male). Audience included both internal and external stakeholders.

Minutes

Due to COVID-19 regulations it was not possible to organise the face-to-face event and the session was organised online. The Information session started with welcome speech and included presentations and discussion. The presentations mainly covered information about GEP activities per each area, key priority areas on which GEP is focused, main strategy adopted by SRNSFG and its main goals in frame of the CALIPER project. Besides that, the speakers stressed the importance/need for the gender equality in STEM and significance of three ERA priorities. Also, during the session upcoming collaborative actions were discussed more precisely.

Gender Equality issues are common among different stakeholders and institutions. Some institutions have already started working towards gender direction and shared interesting and useful examples of particular activities.

The session covered its main goals such as the raising awareness about gender equality issues in STEM and launching and presenting GEP. GEP's actions were supported by stakeholders and they expressed their interest in further meetings. In addition, after the announcement of GEP's launch future collaborative activities can be expected and implemented.

For the second online session it is recommended to increase the number of participants - invite and engage more stakeholders (this significantly depends on COVID-19 situation) and provide more detailed information about the ongoing implementation process and results of the implemented GEP activities.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 7 SRNSFG online awareness session & public event snapshot

Agenda

6 October, 2021

Tbilisi, Georgia

**Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia - SRNSFG Hub:
Linking Research and Innovation for Gender Equality**

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/8159309443?pwd=WUtQYm1CaW8rbFoxbFBtMUNuRTl6dz09>
Meeting ID: 815 930 9443
Passcode: iZOKLx

Agenda

15:45 – 16:00 Registration

Upon registration, all participants will have the opportunity to check their headphones and microphone

16:00 – 16:15 Evaluation Review, ERA connection, Presentation of GEP (particular actions, dates);

Prof. Nino Gachechiladze (SRNSFG);

16:15 – 16:30 Institutional Communication (particular actions with dates), collaboration actions and planned activities;

Dr. Rusudan Jobava (SRNSFG);

16:30 – 16:45 Changes in scientific direction – collaboration activities (with dates)

Lana Davituliანი (SRNSFG);

16:45 – 17:00 Gender related problems in academic environment and existing regulations

Prof. Tamar Gurchiani (Ilia State University);

17:00 – 17:15 Sharing Best practice

Prof. Nani Matcharashvili (GIPA);

17:15 – 17:25 Summary

Figure 8 SRNSFG online awareness session & public event agenda (photo)

3.2.2 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

During the workshop the upcoming activities for the GEP implementation was overviewed and the main existing and potential barriers were discussed. The workshop was organised on 27.10.2021. It started at 15:00 and lasted around 1.5 hours.

Agenda

Presentation of the GEP to the GEP working group

Round table – discussion

Table 11 SRNSFG internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

The workshop was attended by all members of GEP working group and two organisation team members.

Minutes

Due to COVID-19 regulations the meeting was organised online via zoom platform. The Workshop started with brief overview of the upcoming GEP tasks and then continued with the discussion on the main barriers and issues.

GEP WG overviewed different scenarios for the implementation process and in details discussed the main issues related to the upcoming tasks. Besides that, the group overviewed the potential resistances and the ways to overcome them. Participants shared their experiences with different GEP areas and activities and their opinions on the potential solutions of particular issues. Also, during the workshop the group analysed the existing innovation environment and the best methods of sharing GEP experiences and practices with external environment and stakeholders.

Main goals of the workshop were reached during the meeting. Based on the organised discussion, particular action plan was elaborated for the effective targeting and preventing different barriers and issues in GEP implementation process.

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 9 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the SRNSFG events

3.2.3 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

The WIN event was organised on 30th of April onsite. The event aimed to highlight and value women's led innovations presenting startups and raising awareness. The main goals of the event were achieved successfully. The event started at 12:00 and lasted till 16:00.

Agenda

“Women in Innovation”

Tbilisi, April 30, 2022, Rooms Hotel, M. Kostava Str. 14

12:00 -12:15	Registration of participants; welcome coffee
12:15 – 12:25	Opening remarks and project presentation
12:25 – 12:35	Inese Gavarane, SRNSFG Twinning Office, Georgia; Kirsten Kienzler, DLR Project management Agency, Germany – “STI system improvement: more increased opportunities for Women in Innovation”
12:35 - 12:45	Nino Rechtsteiner, Ecobauli – “CO2 negative & affordable construction system from natural materials”
12:45 – 12:55	Mariam Menabde, Caucasus University – “Modernisation facades of the typical residential houses”
13:10 - 13:20	Ketevan and Tamar Bosikashvili, Biterium AI, technological startup– “Cardiovascular diseases and artificial intelligence”
13:20 – 13:30	Lili Petriashvili, GTU – “Contemporary challenges of global data digital transformation”
13:30 - 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 14:10	Ia Kusradze, G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology - “Phage Pastilles for prevention and treatment of oral cavity and upper respiratory tract infections”
14:10 – 14:20	Natia Jalagonia, Ilia Vekua Sukhumi Institute of Physics and Technology - “Developing of electromagnetic interference shielding materials based on new polymer composites to minimize electromagnetic radiation of electronic devices, wires and coaxial cables”
14:20 – 14:30	Maguli Bedineishvili, GPU – “ The paradigm of biometric technologies”
14:30-14:40	Tamar Berberashvili, GPU - “Development of Energy Management System (EMS) by Smart Controller for Connecting Microgenerators to the Electrical Distribution Network and Consumers”
14:40 - 15:00	Closing of the event

Participants

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

A total of 52 participants (48 females and 4 males) attended the WIN event. Most of them were representatives from academia, industry and public sector. The participants list included stakeholders from R&I Hub and successful women scientists and startups.

More specifically, the types of stakeholders participated in the event, are displayed below:

Public sector	17
Industry	4
Higher Education	31

Table 12 SRNSFG WIN event stakeholder type of participants

Minutes

At the beginning of the session after the opening remarks, CALIPER project team presented the main aspects of the project and its main goals and activities. Also, during the event CALIPER team presented the Annual Female Scientists Award established as one of the GEP activities. It was stressed that the Award represents a good opportunity for female scientists. Unfortunately, it was not possible to identify the winner before and give the award during the WIN event, since the applications revision process required more time.

Besides that, CALIPER team presented a special section on the SRNSFG website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM/research it was also mentioned that Foundation will be glad to receive different suggestions for the website section about successful women scientists and role models from external stakeholders.

After the presentation of startups and innovations led by women, each session included questions/answers session. Different topics and presentations also raised discussions among the participants. In addition, participants were interested by presented products and shared personal contacts among each other's.

During the WIN event it was possible raise awareness on gender equality and strengthen the significance of role of STEM field for women, also different projects and startups stressing successful women careers were presented. The event gave the opportunity to participants share their information and personal experience among other participants and make a start for future collaborations and cooperation.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 10 SRNSFG WIN event photos

Recoding of the event

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LaOeNFupxMPc_3CpK-Ljlxycsvm3UmU?usp=sharing

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

3.3 Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava – Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU BA)

3.3.1 Online awareness session

Introduction

The GEP was forwarded to the members of the AS (Academic Senate) who read it in advance. It was also reviewed within the Legislative commission (composed of AS members). The individual remarks from the review and comments from AS members were discussed with the present CALIPER team members during the AS meeting on 1st Dec. 2021.

Final resolution: The MTF AS discussed the submitted GEP and recommended to adopt the conclusions of the legislative commission:

- 1) Develop a brief strategic framework
- 2) Incorporate the comments in the notes.

This resolution was adopted unanimously (15 votes)

Agenda

Feedback from the AS MTF members, MTF Legislative commission about the presented GEP
Discussion about implementation of the GEP
Resolution of the meeting

Table 13 STU BA online awareness session agenda

Participants

The participants were internal staff, people from the CALIPER team, academic senate members and guests. In total, 21 people attended the meeting.

Minutes

During this meeting, the AS members had opportunity to read and prepare comments about the GEP in advance before the AS meeting, which simplified already difficult discussion. The head of AS, dean and Caliper project leader opened the discussion within the AS. The legislative commission read their statement. The biggest issues seen by the AS members were the length of the GEP (47 pages in Slovak version) with very detailed activities, and strict quotas, given the impression that they promote women disproportionately. The aim was to persuade the AS members to approve the GEP and support its application in practice, as well as to legally define Gender Equality practices that are already in usage at MTF STU BA but are not stated in any legal documents.

The feedback from the Legislative commission was given in advance before the AS meeting. Legislative commission is composed of 6 members of the AS. The meeting of AS MTF took place 1.12.2021 online by using the Google Meet platform and the GEP was discussed with the CALIPER project team members. In the end of the meeting, after heated discussion the final resolution was given by AS members.

Overall, the GEP was presented, discussed, but received negative feedback. Its application will be challenging and alternative solutions to combat the resistances were needed.

Supporting material

Photos

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

3.3.2 Public online event

Introduction

Title: „The 26th International Slovak-Polish Scientific Conference on Machine Modelling and Simulations“.

The event took place on 13-15 of May 2021, onsite in Bardejov, Slovakia, which allowed effective networking and information sharing even after the end of the Open dialog. The presentation was followed by discussion with relevant questions and points of view from both practice and theory.

Agenda

Registration of MMS 2021 participants

Opening ceremony	Dean of FMT TUKE Dr. h. c. Prof., Eng. MSc. Jozef Zajac, Ph.D.
Open dialog on the topic „Gender equality plans as a precondition for participation in the Horizon Europa project scheme ”- within the H2020 project “Linking Research and Innovation for Gender Equality” No.873134, CALIPER	Assoc. Prof. M. A. Dagmar Cagáňová, Ph.D., MTF STU Trnava

Discussion, networking, dinner

Table 14 STU BA Public event agenda

Participants

Number of people present is 54, 13 females and 41 males, mostly composed of Science, education and private sector members.

Minutes

The STU BA representatives participated to the conference: The 26th International Slovak-Polish Scientific Conference on Machine Modelling and Simulations in Hotel Alexander, Bardejovské Kúpele, Slovak Republic on September 13-15th 2021. On behalf of CALIPER, they organised an open dialog on the topic „Gender

equality plans as a precondition for participation in the Horizon Europa project scheme ”- within the H2020 project “Linking Research and Innovation for Gender Equality” No.873134, CALIPER.

The event was composed of a speech from prof. Caganova followed by open discussion from the present public. In the end, the recommendations and findings were summarised, and the audience seemed interested to participate in similar discussions and workshops to motivate and address other people around gender equality.

STU BA has planned to continue activities such as workshops and discussions with the topic of GE and inclusion, and continue with networking.

Supporting material

Photos

Conference opening ceremony, speaker Dr. h. c. mult. prof. Ing. Josef Zajac, CSc., dean Faculty of Manufacturing Technologies with the seat in Presov, Technical University of Kosice

Conference opening ceremony

Conference participants

Figure 11 STU BA public event photos

3.3.3 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

The internal workshop lasted one and a half hours from 10: 00 to 11: 30. Prof. Mgr. Dagmar Caganova PhD. representing STU Bratislava. As a responsible researcher for the H2020 CALIPER, Dagmar provided the introduction of GEP (Gender Equality Plan) within the CALIPER project and initiatives in STUBA. This was

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followed by a presentation of best practice, innovation environment and barriers to GEP implementation at Slovak universities by Ing. Veronika Mešková representing University of Zilina, Mgr. Alena Rusnáková, PhD. representing Technical University of Kosice, prof. PhDr. Alexandra Bitušíková, CSc. representing UMB Banska Bystrica.

Agenda

Introduction of GEP	Gender Equality Plan - Prof. Mgr. Dagmar Caganova PhD
Best practices, innovation environment and barriers to GEP implementation	Ing. Veronika Mešková representing University of Zilina, Mgr. Alena Rusnáková, PhD. representing Technical University of Kosice, prof. PhDr. Alexandra Bitušíková, CSc. representing UMB Banska Bystrica
Open Discussion	

Table 15 STU BA internal workshop agenda

Participants

In total 97 people – 61 women, 36 men participated.

Minutes

The first objective of the public activity was to share opinions and knowledge on the fact that more and more women see their future in studying technical fields. The second objective was to provide inspirational stories of young people in start-ups and successful women in an innovative business environment. The EU influence on equal opportunities could be considered as another objective of the event which was very well elaborated.

Key findings include:

- When talking about change it must start from each person individually
- Be courage, study and get inspired by other Western countries
- Hardworking and proactive approach is the main key to success
- It's not just about relying on top management, it's also about offering them the right ideas and suggestions
- Bc. Anastasia Hnidets a Andrii Hryn presenting start-up at the event did not feel any barriers for doing business in Slovakia as foreigners from Ukraine
- Bc. Yulia Sytar presenting her start-up on the event appreciate Slovakian study and university environment

It could be concluded that the meeting was very well structured, planned, and led by prof. Dagmar Caganova. Despite the small changes in the schedule and the technical problems of the presenters, the event was successful.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 12 Photos from the STU BA combined event

Presentation slides

3.3.4 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

The event started at 12:00 pm on 17th of May 2022. It was held online. The main aim of the event was to raise awareness and promote women working in the STEM field. The target audience were people from the field of University and Science, Business and Government fields. The presentations proved that females also belong in STEM field and they are active in it, although they are not promoted so much. The presentations were inspiring and the discussion and networking were beneficial for both sides, the speakers, as well as the audience.

Agenda

- Success stories by women startpers in the STEM industry
- Discussion on equal opportunities in the STEM industry in Slovakia
- Q&A

*Table 16 STU BA WIN event agenda***Participants**

A total of 97 participants attended the WIN event. 61 were females and 36 were males. The majority, 70 people were from academia and higher education, 5 were policy makers, 4 were civil society representatives, and 18 were industry/private sector representatives.

Minutes

The organising team was composed of Dagmar Caganova who moderated the Win Event, Natalia Hornakova, who was responsible for the organisation of the presentations and Lubica Znamenakova for technical support. The event run online on the platform Google Meet, the invitations were shared both online, by email, on social networks an online as posters in chosen institutions. Methods applied in this event mostly consisted of: Presentation, discussion, and summary of information and facts.

Win event lasted almost two hours. In the first block. Mgr. Alexandra Blažeková presented her successful stories and experiences from Australia and company Staple bread & necessities. Alexandra was followed by Ing. Lenka Hlinková, who presented her concept Female Algorithm, n. o., where Lenka is the Executive Director. Ing. Ivana Nováková was the following presenter, who presented about the start-up center TUKE and her successful career up to now where is the Managing Director of Aponi, s. r. o. The second part, young enthusiastic students Bc. Anastasia Hnidets and Andrii Hryn presented their start-up concept Hoppy, Bc. Diana Lazarenko presented her start-up concept Wardrobe + and as the last lady to finish this block was Bc. Yulia Sytar presented her start-up Psychológ.

The main remarks and key finding of the event are as follows:

- It's not just about relying on top management, it's also about offering them the right ideas and suggestions
- Bc. Anastasia Hnidets a Andrii Hryn presenting start-up at the event did not feel any barriers for doing business in Slovakia as foreigners from Ukraine
- Bc. Yulia Sytar presenting her start-up on the event appreciate Slovakian study and university environment
- All start-up leaders feel support from the management and leader and appreciated the promotion of this event

Main outcomes

- Provide inspirational stories of young people in start-ups and successful women in an innovative business environment.
- The sharing of opinions on why more and more women see their future in studying technical fields.
- Audience was very interested in the start-ups, said many supportive and creative ideas which can help to improve both the start-ups themselves as well to motivate other attendants to find another start-ups and support them

Supporting material**Photos**

Figure 13 Photos from the STU BA WIN event

Supporting material from all three events (Internal workshop with GEP working group - public online event – WIN event)

Agenda

Čas (CET)	Aktivita	Inštitúcia
10:00	Otvorenie, privítanie hostí	STUBA
	Interný workshop	
	prof. Mgr. Dagmar Cagaňová, PhD. Zodpovedná riaditeľka projektu H2020 CALIPER, STU BA „Predstavenie Plánu rodovej rovnosti (GEP) v rámci projektu CALIPER“	STUBA
	Ing. Veronika Mešková H2020 CHANGE projektová manažérka pre UNIZA, koordinátorka úlohy výskumu a vývoja	UNIZA
	Mgr. Alena Rusnáková, PhD. Oddelenie spoločenských vied, TUKE	TUKE
	prof. PhDr. Alexandra Blážeková, CSc. Riaditeľka Univerzitného centra pre medzinárodné projekty, UMB Banská Bystrica	UMB
	prof. Ing. Miloš Pollak, PhD. Dekan FPEDAS UNIZA „Zamestnávanie žien v cestnej nákladnej doprave na pozícií vodič/vodička“	FPEDAS UNIZA
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
11:30 – 12:00	Prestávka	
12:00	Mladí ľudia a inovácie - Win event	
	Mgr. Alexandra Blažeková Staple bread & necessities, manažérka	MTF STU Staple bread & necessities
	Ing. Lenka Hlinková Ženský algoritmus, n. o., výkonná riaditeľka	Ženský algoritmus, n. o.
	Ing. Ivana Nováková Konateľka spoločnosti Aponi, s. r. o., start-up centrum TUKE	Aponi, s. r. o.
	Prezentácie start-up projektov študentiek a študentov pod vedením doc. Ing. Michala Baloga, CSc. (vedúci KPIL, FVT TUKE)	
	Bc. Anastasia Hnidets a Andrii Hryn	FVT
	Bc. Diana Lazarenko	FVT

Čas (CET)	Aktivita	Inštitúcia
	Bc. Yulia Sytar	FVT
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
13:50 – 14:00	Coffee break	
14:00	Online awareness session	
	prof. Ing. Milan Edl, PhD. Dekan, Strojnícka fakulta ZCU Pízeň „HR award of excellence“	ZCU Pízeň
	prof. Ing. Jozef Rístevej, PhD. Proroktor pre medzinárodné vzťahy a marketing, ŽU „Žilinská univerzita v kontexte internacionalizácie a inštitucionálnych zmien“	UNIZA
	Mgr. Zuzana Štaňáková, PhD Sekcia podpory vedy „Nástroj inštitucionálnej zmeny - GEP CVTI SR“	CVTI
	prof. Ing. Robert Štefko, PhD. Dekan FMEaO PU	PU
	Otvorená diskusia – O&O	All
15:00	Záver podujatia	STUBA

Strana 2 z 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 14 STU BA all day event agenda

Event poster

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 15 STU BA all day event communication material

3.4 Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

3.4.1 Online awareness session & Public online event

Introduction

The official presentation of ULB's GEP in STEM was carried out onsite on the 9th November 2021 from 5pm to 7pm followed by a drink (ULB's premises). During the event, the University and STEM faculties top management took the floor and showed their support to the Plan. The GEP was also presented in detail by a member of the CALIPER team and two external stakeholders engaged in promoting gender equality in STEM were also invited to speak. There were two Q&A moments in which the public could ask questions and exchange with the speakers. A total of 66 people attended the event.

Agenda

17h	Welcome of the participants	
17h15-17h25	Welcome speech of the ULB authorities	Annemie Schaus, <i>Rector</i> Michel Verstraeten, <i>Vice-Rector for Academic Policy in charge of Diversity and Gender Policy</i>
17h25-17h30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video presentation of the CALIPER project • Video of policy support for the CALIPER project 	
17h30-17h50	Presentation of the ULB STEM Gender Equality Plan + Q&A	Sara Aguirre, <i>researcher and project officer of the CALIPER project at ULB</i>
17h50-18h	Gender equality in higher education in the Brussels-Wallonian Federation	Valérie Glatigny, <i>Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research</i>

18h-18h30	Women and girls' experiences in science and technology + Q&A	Marie-Christine Creton, <i>former Director of the National Institute of Applied Sciences in Strasbourg and General Secretary of the association Femmes et Sciences</i> Dr. Ir. Laure Waegemans, <i>R&D Product & Process Innovation Director, Procter & Gamble</i>
18h30-18h40	Closing speech of the ULB STEM faculty authorities	Frédéric Robert & Olivier Markowitch, <i>Deans of the Polytechnic school of Brussels and the Faculty of Science</i>
19h	Drink	

Table 17 ULB awareness raising & public event agenda

Participants

A total of 66 people attended the event (32 women, 21 men, 5 „other“ and 8 did not mark their gender). They were members of ULB and members of the R&I Hub. A Minister was present and the representatives of 4 other Ministries as well.

Minutes

To officially present ULB's Gender equality plan in STEM to both the University's community and external stakeholders. The evening conference with several presentations from the University and STEM faculties top management, the CALIPER team and external stakeholders engaged in promoting gender equality in STEM. The GEP was presented in detail, both the gender assessment carried out, the gender strategy and the 20 actions included in it. The conference lasted 2 hours and it was followed by a drink that allowed participants to keep on exchanging on gender equality in STEM. A QR code was created so that participants could download the summary of the GEP to consult its contents.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 16 ULB awareness raising & public event photos

3.4.2 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

A meeting was organised on 13 December 2021 with the members of the working group to discuss about progress in the implementation of GEP actions, as well as resistances and obstacles. The important questions of communication and awareness raising were deeply discussed.

Agenda

Presentation of the GEP actions by the CALIPER team for the first semester

Presentation of the GEP actions by the CALIPER team for the second semester

Table 18 ULB Internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Participants

A total of 10 members of the GW participated (5 women and 5 men).

Minutes

The session was organised online on 13 December 2021 and lasted 1 hour. The session started with a presentation by the CALIPER team of the GEP actions currently being implemented (1st semester) according to the designed timeframe. Obstacles and resistances were identified for some actions. Then, the actions to be implemented in the 2nd semester were also presented. The CALIPER team presented then the communication and awareness raising activities carried out until then and invited the participants to reflect and discuss on how to improve awareness raising to increase the level of support, especially for actions for which there may be more resistance.

Resistances/obstacles identified

- Measure 7 (proposal for gender balance in advisory bodies): There is a need to find out what has been stuck (timing issue? other obstacles?). Based on this, to think of solutions, strategies to put in place. Idea: discuss it in the Academic Forum (Rector + deans) to explain the measure to the deans. If the measure does not pass now, they have 2 years to prepare the ground. It is normal that resistance is emerging now. --> To do: the Vice-Rector will ask the Rector for more information on resistances.
- Measure 15 (WIN event): given the health situation, the date may have to be postponed. The decision will be made in early January 2022 depending on the evolution of the situation.

Reflections on communication activities and awareness raising strategy

- Findings/Observations: The CALIPER project and the GEP have been presented by the team at several events. There is the impression that they are not well known by staff and students. Sometimes students have the impression that nothing is moving or that it is moving very slowly.

Discussion

- The dissemination of information can be improved by establishing a closer link between the chair of the gender commission, the dean and the CALIPER team (e.g., inform the gender commission of follow-up actions and upcoming actions).
- It is normal that people do not know the specific contents of the GEP.
- It is necessary to inform as actions are implemented. Rather than doing abstract awareness raising disconnected from the actions, they must put in place initiatives to accompany these actions.
- Informing about concrete actions is the best form of awareness raising. This is when debates/resistance emerge and the institution can discuss and raise awareness about specific problems.
- Important: know what information to give to whom and when.

Overall, there is a general support for the GEP and the values it represents. There is however resistance/obstacles for some specific actions. The best way to deal with it is to anticipate it, understand its reasons and to organise concrete awareness raising activities targeting those specific resistances. It is also very important to be transparent and to communicate about what is being done, targeting the right people.

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 17 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the ULB events

3.4.3 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

The WIN event took place on the 30th of April 2022 from 9am to 4pm, at the ULB Plaine - Faculty of Sciences (Building Forum). The main objective of this event was to bring almost 100 young girls (12-15 years old) closer to the STEM subjects. Girls gone through 4 workshops to learn hands-on skills in STEM, to gain a sense of confidence and belonging in STEM, to meet local STEM role models and were encouraged to take up long-term STEM careers.

Agenda

07:00	Arrival of the organisers - opening of the premises
08:30	Arrival and briefing of the volunteers
09:00	Arrival of the participants + snack & goodies
10:00	Opening ceremony – Introduction by g4g and ULB + speech by a role model (Nathalie Stephenne from Women In Copernicus)
11:00	2 workshops – each 45 minutes
12:50	Lunch (humus, sandwich, cookies and juice)
13:40	2 workshops – each 45 minutes
15:30	Closing ceremony – evaluation forms & group pictures
16:00	END – parents pick up girls + storage
18:00	Closing doors

Table 19 ULB WIN event agenda

Participants

The WIN event had 93 participants. All of them were girls, mainly between 12 and 15 years old (95%), with only a few younger and older girls. They also rated the socio-economic and cultural statue of the participants. They had this indication considering which school the girls are coming from. They had almost 1/3 from low socio-economical school level (32%). The majority were coming from school with a high socio-economical level (57%). Also, few participants came because their parents were running a workshop (11%).

Minutes

First, participants and volunteers were invited to an opening ceremony. They took this moment to introduce the event and promote some role models. Then, the organisers invited them to join their group leader. Each volunteer was responsible for guiding a group of 10 girls to each workshop. Some group leaders were also role models as young women and men working in science. During the morning they visited 2 workshops, where they run funny and interactive STEM experiment. For the lunch, they gathered everyone in the principal auditorium. Volunteers were invited to eat with participants and take this time to share a good moment. During the afternoon, they went with their group to two other workshops. At the end of the workshops, the participants shared their feedback for the session. The organisers asked the participants if they enjoyed the day and they encouraged them to share their favorite moments of the day.

Overall, during the Opening ceremony, the participants discussed about the gap between men and women in science, and how the girls can be motivated, with emphasis their competencies. To strengthen this process, the floor was given to role models, to show them how they can empower themselves and support other girls. The personal stories that were shared, aimed at motivating and inspiring young girls to pursue a career in science.

During the workshops, the girls had the chance to do simple science experiments and exercises. These include:

- A virtual visit to a high-voltage installation to illustrate electricity transmission and make it more concrete, and to illustrate this complementary trade to electricity production.
- Discover electrical circuits in a fun way, using everyday objects to raise awareness of the importance of electricity in less privileged countries for the empowerment of less privileged girls.
- Discovering 3D printing - 2D Design - Vinyl cutting - Heat press - Garment customisation to understand the stages of 2D printing and how the machines work
- Workshop explaining how every object is calculated and need to be calculated to guarantee the safety of all and the durability of the renewed objects, to explain why calculations are essential to ensure the proper functioning and durability of objects/works and the safety of all.
- Workshop to discover the hidden face of water and its role in the phenomenon of osmosis that is constantly taking place in our bodies without people realising it.
- behind the scenes of an architectural project to raise awareness of the 'sustainable development' aspects of industrial projects to show the multitude of trades involved in the realisation of a large-scale project such as the hull factory
- Measurement of the circumference of the Earth based on the method of Eratosthenes.
- The mysteries of light. How are rainbows formed? What is a colour? Practical construction of a spectrograph with the help of a CD, to better understand the instrumental approach to light.
- Experiments with essential oils, with the challenge of recreate certain scents (Coca Cola scent, Rose scent, etc.), to learn how combinations of fragrances can create very fun and different scents, to raise awareness of the professions of perfumers and chemistry in general.
- Experiments with fruits with simple tasks (extract the juice from red cabbage, pour it into 5-6 cups and then add different chemicals/materials), to observe the different color shifts and link them to the pH change.
- Building an origami microscope and observe different items with it, to discover how microscopes work and how the objects are demonstrated under them.

- Workshop to discover the physico-chemical properties of water through two techniques: a chromatography workshop ("Chromatographic flowers"), and diffusion and osmosis ("Juicy strawberries").

Main results and improvements of the action in terms of gender equality

- Young girls enjoyed the activities, and the organisers motivated them to follow sciences studies
- This event held ULB institutions to work in this sense and to promote awareness about the importance of science vulgarisation, especially towards young women.

Sustainability of institutional change

- The promotion of a long term collaboration with g4g to establish this event on a permanent basis was initiated.

Supporting material

Photos

[[Photos of the event](#)]

Figure 18 ULB WIN event photo

WIN event material

Vos élèves sont invitées au "g4g Day ULB" !

greenlight for girls (g4g) est une ONG internationale qui a pour but de familiariser les filles aux STEM (Science, Technologie, ingénierie et Mathématiques). L'Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB) et g4g s'allient pour inviter 150 filles âgées de 12 à 18 ans (provenant de différentes écoles bruxelloises) à poursuivre leurs études dans les STEM. Nous organisons notre "g4g Day ULB" dans les locaux de l'université pour une journée d'exploration où chaque participante pourra découvrir plusieurs ateliers interactifs et amusants.

C'est un événement gratuit, en français, et le repas est fourni!

Réserver vos places!

Samedi 30 avril 2022
9h - 16h

ULB, Campus de la Plaine

Pour vous inscrire, veuillez directement consulter le lien donné à l'école par nos organisateurs. Des questions? Contacter: Meriam.Hammou@ulb.be

L'événement est spécifiquement conçu pour des jeunes filles afin de leur montrer les différents aspects que peuvent prendre les études et les carrières scientifiques.

99%

Le retour des filles ayant participé à l'événement est très positif. La note moyenne donnée est de 9,5/10!

34%

Nous constatons qu'après notre journée g4g, 34% des filles se voient plus intéressées par les sujets STEM.

2%

Les étudiantes ont déclaré une augmentation de 2% du nombre de femmes dans les carrières STEM sur les 10 dernières années.

Notre journée...

- 09:00: Déplacement et collation
- 10:00: Accueil et cérémonie d'ouverture
- 11:00: Atelier 1
- 12:00: Atelier 2
- 12:30: Déjeuner
- 13:30: Atelier 3
- 14:15: Atelier 4
- 15:00: Cérémonie de clôture
- 16:00: Départ

Notre journée permet de :

- Faire découvrir les différentes carrières STEM
- Concier de l'expérience des filles qui ont réussi en STEM
- Mettre en contact les filles avec des expertes STEM
- Développer l'alphabétisation pratique
- Développer des compétences de communication
- Développer des capacités d'entraide et de solidarité
- Améliorer le sens de la carrière

Pour plus d'information : www.greenlightforgirls.org

Figure 19 ULB WIN event workshop material

3.5 School of electrical and computing engineering – National Technical University of Athens (ECE-NTUA)

3.5.1 Public online event

Introduction

Title of the event: “Development of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School of the NTUA” (external infosession).

The first informative session was held on 26th November 2021. The session titled, “Development of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School of the NTUA” was organised online and was attended online by 19 representatives from 7 Academic Institutions, (including members of the Gender Equality Committee of NTUA and the University of Thessaly), 3 Research Centers and 4 Public Bodies, including the General Secretariat for Demographic and Family Policy and Gender Equality. The development team presented the Gender Equality Plan of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering and its development with the CALIPER methodology (www.caliper-project.eu). The session last approximately 2,5 hours.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Responsible and duration
11:40 – 11:40	Opening and welcome speech	Vice dean Prof. D. Askounis
11:50 – 12:20	Presentation of the following topics: EU policies on GE in research, ERA objectives, arguments in favor of gender equality, good practices in gender equality actions and plans.	CALIPER Team of ECE-NTUA Dr Maro Bafaloukou, Ms Hera Neofytou
12:10-12:20	“Policies of the National Equality Agency - National Action Plan for Equality 2021-2025”	Ms Sofia Nikolaou (General Secretariat for Demographic and Family Policy and Gender Equality)
12:20-12:30	Development of the Gender Equality Plan of the National Technical University of Athens	Dr. Maria Flouri (Member of the NTUA Gender Equality Committee)
12:30-12:50	Q&A	
12:50-13:00	Break	
13:00-13:30	Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan of ECE-NTUA	Dr Emmanouil Ntanos
13:30-14:00	Discussion	

Table 20 ECE-NTUA public event agenda

Participants

The first online session was attended by 19 representatives from 7 Academic Institutions, (including members of the Gender Equality Committee of NTUA and the University of Thessaly), 3 Research Centers and 4 Public Bodies, including the General Secretariat for Demographic and Family Policy and Gender Equality.

Type of external stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia & universities (7)	National Technical University of Athens, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, University of Patras, University of Western Macedonia, Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences, University of Thessaly, International Hellenic University

Research Centres (3)	Institute of Educational Policy, National Centre of Scientific Research "Demokritos", Foundation for Research & Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
Ministries/Government (1)	General Secretariat for Demographic and Family Policy and Gender Equality (Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs)
Public sector (3)	Region of Central Macedonia, e-Trikala, ELGO-DIMITRA

Table 21 ECE-NTUA public event participant stakeholder type

Minutes

The goal of the online first informative session was to present the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School of the NTUA to external stakeholders and discuss methodological issues regarding the development of GEPs. Additionally, the session included presentations on the EU and national gender strategies, GEPs in practice and the upcoming NTUA GEP.

The ECE-NTUA team presented also the results of their participation in an online training session for Greek stakeholders (academia, research, public sector organisations), on the GEP requirements of the Horizon Europe programme (9/11/2021). The team was invited to briefly present experiences and lessons learned from the development of the ECE-NTUA GEP through CALIPER. The participants showed interest in the details of the GEP, and the process for its development. The session included introductory presentations on the framework of GEPs in Europe, the national strategies, and the upcoming GEP of the NTUA. The European framework was presented by the team, while an expert from the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs presented the policies of the National Gender Equality Plan, and Dr Maria Flouri, also a member of the NTUA Gender Equality Committee, presented the progress of the institution's GEP. Finally, the activities and the methodology of ECE-NTUA GEP were shared with the participants.

Afterwards, the team presented the CALIPER project, the methodology and the results for the internal assessment. The team also presented the stakeholders involved in the development of the GEP, the process used, and the resulting actions. Finally, the monitoring and evaluation methodology was discussed, including the establishment of indicators and result levels. The session ended with a discussion on best practices and relevant topics.

During the discussion various stakeholders noted the need of funding to support Gender Equality Plans. Some participants reported that they face difficulties during the process of collecting data.

The participants were pleased with the discussion and the CALIPER team gained positive feedback, since they received fruitful information to support the development of their own GEPs or enhance the implementation of the existing ones. It was noted that an open dialogue would be rather helpful.

Supporting material

Photos

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 20 ECE-NTUA public event photos

3.5.2 Online awareness session

Introduction

Title of the event: “Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School of the NTUA” (internal infosession).

The online session was held on December 2, 2021. It lasted approximately two hours. The goal of the online informative session was to launch and present the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School of the NTUA to internal stakeholders. The team organised the session to communicate about the Gender Equality Plan and its actions. Moreover, through the presentation of the actions the team succeed to raise awareness to the members of the School on gender equality issues.

Agenda

Time	Activity	Responsible and duration
12:00 – 12:10	Opening and welcome speech	Vice Dean Prof. Dimitris Askounis
12:10 – 12:30	Presentation of the following topics: EU policies on GE in research, National Policies, ERA objectives, arguments in favor of gender equality, good practices in gender equality actions and plans.	CALIPER Team of ECE-NTUA Dr Maro Bafaloukou, Ms Hera Neofytou
12:30-12:40	“Development of the Gender Equality Plan of the NTUA”	Dr Emmanouil Ntanos (Dr Maria Flouri of the NTUA GEC was scheduled to present but was unable to do so due to unforeseen circumstances)
12:30-12:45	Q&A	
12:45 – 13:00	Break	
13:00-13:40	Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan of ECE-NTUA	Dr Emmanouil Ntanos
13:40-14:00	Discussion	

Table 22 ECE-NTUA Online awareness session agenda

Participants

The online session was attended by 33 members of the School’s academic, administrative, laboratory, technical and research staff. The breakdown of the attendees was the following

Type of internal stakeholder	Stakeholders
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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Academic staff	2 males
Administrative staff	3 females / 1 male
Laboratory Teaching staff	2 females
Laboratory Technical staff	3 males
Research staff	4 females / 18 males

Table 23 ECE-NTUA Online awareness session audience

Minutes

The development team presented the Gender Equality Plan of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering and its development with the CALIPER methodology. The presentation was attended by members of the School's academic, administrative, laboratory, technical and research staff. The aim was to present the methodology followed by the CALIPER team to develop the GEP as well as to inform about the internal situation of the School. Moreover, the presentation of GEP actions shows the pathway that the staff should follow (e.g. language in administrative documents).

The session included introductory presentations on the framework of GEPs in Europe, the national strategies, and the upcoming GEP of the NTUA.

The European framework was presented by the team while Dr Maria Flouri, also a member of the NTUA Gender Equality Committee, presented the progress of the institution's GEP. Finally, the activities and the methodology of ECE-NTUA GEP were shared with the participants.

Afterwards, the team presented the CALIPER project, the methodology and the results for the internal assessment. The team also presented the stakeholders involved in the development of the GEP, the process used, and the resulting actions. Finally, the monitoring and evaluation methodology was discussed, including the establishment of indicators and result levels. The focus of the session was less on the methodological aspects of developing a GEP and more on the results of the internal assessment and the actions of the GEP. The session ended with a discussion on the actions of the GEP and its importance.

No resistances were encountered at the meeting itself. It should be noted, though, that participation was lower than expected, given that invitations were forwarded to all Academic, Technical and Laboratory staff. The faculty expects that if some concrete initial results are achieved, the visibility and legitimacy of the GEP will be strengthened and the engagement from the staff will be increased.

Most of the participants were not aware for the internal situation of the School regarding the allocation of men and women in staff and students. The participants noted the importance of taking into account gender in the School's strategy, as well as the fact that this is the first time this takes place. The organisers also received ideas for future gender-related actions from the participants.

They were updated on the progress of the alumni network of the Liaison Office, by a representative of the administrative staff informed that the Liaison Office (receiving initial registrations), so gender-oriented actions could possibly start within this academic year.

The participants were encouraged to disseminate the information to their colleagues. Overall, the CALIPER team received positive feedback, the participants welcomed the activities and agreed to support the sustainability of the GEP.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 21 ECE-NTUA Online awareness session photos

3.5.3 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

Title of the event: “GEP implementation at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the NTUA”. The workshop was held online on the 18th of February, 2022, from 12.30-14.00 EET. The internal workshop was used to present the current progress to the WG, and the discuss the planned activities for the forthcoming period. Possible challenges, and obstacles regarding the implementation process were also discussed. The session took place with the participation of members of the GEP WG and the project team.

Agenda

- Discussing the organisation of the the Women in Innovation –event (event content, selection of speakers, venue arrangements, online/physical/ hybrid implementation, administrative issues and procurement).
- Discussing with the WG the integration of the gender dimension into teaching through the implementation of lectures and the elaboration of seminars. Special focus was given to the creation of material regarding gender and energy policy.
- Organisation of the internal workshop on "Gender sensitive institutional communication".
- Informing the WG about the process of establishing of the Gender Equality Office and its foreseen cooperation with the Gender Equality Committee.
- Discussing the establishment of appropriate mechanisms to handle gender violence/sexual harassment cases, and the collaboration with the NTUA Gender Equality Committee on this issue.

Table 24 ECE-NTUA Internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

The present members (total 9 attendees) of the working group were the following :

N.	Female/male	Position
2	M	Researcher
1	F	Research and teaching staff
1	M	Administrative staff
1	M	Laboratory Staff
1	M	CALIPER project team member
3	F	CALIPER project team member

Table 25 ECE-NTUA Internal workshop participants

Minutes

The CALIPER Team after a brief overview of the passed activities, continued with the presentation of the planned actions. Firstly, the Working Group discussed the WIN event preparation (presentations, venue,

representatives). Another topic discussed was the integration on the gender dimension into teaching through the implementation of lectures (7.1.1) – suggestions were made on the course contents and the people that need to be contacted. Moreover, the WG shared thoughts and ideas about the collaborative action) training workshop on “Gender sensitive institutional communication” (11.3), regarding the time of implementation and the content of the workshop. The WG considered the possible synergies of internal and external stakeholders. The CALIPER Team discussed with the WG the progress made regarding the Gender Equality Office (4.2.1). Finally, the WG were updated on the approach of the NTUA GEC for the handling of bias and gender violence cases, and how the school might cooperate with the committee in this matter. (9.1.1).

The session was held online via Microsoft Teams. The CALIPER team used a single presentation to move through the agenda and the relevant topics. When discussing future activities and how to implement them, the project team transferred the ideas and suggestions of the WG members as notes directly on the presentation, thus making them visible to all attendees.

The upcoming GEP actions were presented and discussed. The GEP WG members discussed solutions to overcome any possible obstacles/resistances regarding the GEP implementation process. The WG members were keen on cooperating to succeed positive outcome. Overall, the meeting was constructive. Note that at the time of this report, a number of the ideas generated were put into practice (e.g. regarding the WIN event, and the gender content of energy policy courses)

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 22 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the ECE-NTUA events

3.5.4 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

The Women in Innovation (WIN) event took place on the 8th of April 2022, 10.00 – 13.30. The event was hybrid. Participants had the opportunity to attend both online, through the MS Teams platform, and physically, in the Multimedia Amphitheater of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

The main objective of the event was to present experiences of women with a strong presence in innovation and entrepreneurship, help highlight women-led innovations and develop strong links with the innovation and business environment. Among the things that were discussed were topics such as:

- Success stories of women's career paths.
- Good practices for the promotion of female entrepreneurship.
- Female contribution to the innovative entrepreneurship and ways of empowerment.
- Successful actions that have adopted gender sensitive policies.
- Prospects for gender dimension integration into innovative entrepreneurship.
- Discussion on business opportunities that support women entrepreneurs.

Agenda

The WIN Event Agenda was structured into 6 (six) sections.

Welcoming speech and Event's kick off	Professor Dimitrios Askounis
Presentation: CALIPER – Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality	Dr. Emmanouil Ntanos, Project Manager
Presentation: 101: Why to do IT	Mrs. Maggy Kontou, Co founder and Lead UI/UX Designer of SimpleApps
Presentation: My road to entrepreneurship. The impact of academia	Mrs. Ioanna Staneglouidi, Co founder and Chief Risk Officer of Finclude
Presentation: Women contribution towards innovative entrepreneurship	Mrs. Roula Bachtalia, Director and Steering Committee member at the egg - enter•grow•go
Presentation: The innovative female mind	Dr. Riva Lava, Head of the NTUA GE Committee and Associate Professor in the School of Architecture.

Participants

39 people online and 20 people in person attended the event, 39 of them were women and 20 of them were men. All participants signed a GDPR statement, agreeing that all email addresses (if provided) will be used to communicate information related to this event such as invitations and updates, only up until the end of the event. Furthermore, the list of participants will be retained as a record of the event's history for up to four years after the end of the event. The participants were mainly researchers, academic personnel (professors, associates, and administrative personnel), representatives from public bodies, members of the R&I Hub and a small number of students.

Minutes

The event was widely disseminated not only within the NTUA but also in other Greek Universities.

The main goal was to attract a satisfactory number of students, as well as academic and administrative personnel, in order to gain insight from the event, as well as to create strong links with the business environment.

The organisation and implementation of the WIN event was a collaborative process. At a School level, the GEP Working Group, the CALIPER Team and the Communication Office were involved, while at an Institutional level the GE Committee and the NTUA Career Office assisted in the dissemination process.

The Event's structure was designed by the CALIPER Team with the assistance of the GEP Working Group. Discussions were held with the GEP WG regarding the optimum place and time of the event, the most appropriate guest profiles, as well as regarding the organisation of the event's dissemination (participants target groups, means of dissemination etc).

The action reached the results and objectives that were set for the short term. Indeed, in the short term the main purpose of the action was to contribute to increased female researchers' confidence, well-being, job satisfaction as well as improve the understanding of career advancement requisites, etc. Also it aimed at strengthening women mentees' professional and/or leadership skills and career prospects through planning,

prioritising, networking and insights into organisational norms, processes and policies. According to the result of the evaluation activities, these objectives were successfully reached. Overall the evaluation of the action was very positive both from the mentors and the mentees side. 9 out of 10 mentors declared to be interested in repeating the experience. On the side of mentees all participants reported to be satisfied by the support received and that they will advise other colleagues to take part in the programme in the next editions. According to the results of the evaluation activities, the program also helped in raising the awareness about the topic of gender equality both among mentors and mentees. Therefore, the action improved the awareness on gender equality issues in the institution even though at a small scale. The continuation of the action with a second mentoring programme in the second iteration will further increase the awareness and the results also considering it aims at widening the number of participants in the program.

The successful implementation of the first edition of the program has been discussed in the frame of a meeting with the top management, which showed to be interested in adopting the measure as a permanent one. The second step will be the formal approval by Committee in September 2022, during which details about how to concretely ensure the action will be incorporated as a permanent activity in the Institutional structure. A calculation of the resources mainly in terms of staff costs will be done and the decision to either hire a dedicated person or to identify an employee to be responsible for the program will be taken.

The WIN event implementation reached its goals which included to share experiences of women in innovation and entrepreneurship, highlight women-led innovations and develop strong links with the innovation and business environment. The event indeed created more links with the innovation and business environment, and 5 new members of the R&I Hub, were attracted through the WIN event.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 23 ECE-NTUA WIN event photos

WIN event recording

<https://onedrive.live.com/?authkey=%21AD1e0L1iL4oJdIQ&cid=18452E1612CF9759&id=18452E1612CF9759%2133054&parId=18452E1612CF9759%2133053&o=OneUp>

Poster

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Τεχνολογία, επιχειρηματικότητα, και
καινοτομίες ευαίσθητες στο φύλο

Ημερίδα
8 Απριλίου 2022
10:00 – 13:30

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Πολυτεχνειούπολη Ζωγράφου
και μέσω Διαδικτύου

Πρόγραμμα
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ΕΜΠ, Πρόεδρος της
Επιτροπής Ισότητας
Φύλων ΕΜΠ

Έλενα Μπάρλα
Ιδρύτρια και ΔΣ της
Among Doctors

Ιωάννα Στανεγλούδη
Συνιδρύτρια και Chief Risk
Officer , Finclude

Καλλιόπη Δαλακλειδή
Ερευνήτρια, Πρόεδρος
του IEEE Greece Section
Women in Engineering
Affinity Group

Μάγκυ Κοντού
Συνιδρύτρια - Lead
Product & UI/UX Designer,
SimpleApps

Ρούλα Μπαχαλιιά
Διευθύντρια & μέλος ΣΕ,
egg - enter*grow*go

Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο
Σχολή Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών
και Μηχανικών Υπολογιστών
Εργαστήριο Συστημάτων Αποφασίσεων και Διαχείρισης

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Το έργο έχει χρηματοδοτηθεί από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης "Ορίζοντας 2020", στο πλαίσιο της Συμφωνίας Επιχορήγησης Αρ. 8733134

Figure 24 ECE-NTUA WIN event promotional poster

Agenda & speakers

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Πρόγραμμα:		Συζήτηση πάνελ	
09:30 – 10:00	Προσέλευση συμμετεχόντων	12.30-13.25	Προσκεκλημένες:
10.00 – 10.15	Καλωσόρισμα και έναρξη ημερίδας κ. Δημήτριος Ασκούνης, Καθηγητής Σχολής Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών & Μηχανικών Υπολογιστών ΕΜΠ, Επιστημονικός Υπεύθυνος CALIPER		κα. <u>Ελενα Μπάρλα</u> , Ιδρύτρια & Διευθύνουσα σύμβουλος της Among Doctors, Διευθύντρια του τμήματος Ψηφιακού Μετασχηματισμού και Βιώσιμης Καινοτομίας στην Stanton Chase Αθήνας
10.15 – 10.30	Εισήγηση: CALIPER – Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality κ. Εμμανουήλ Ντάνος, Συντονιστής Ομάδας		κα. <u>Ιωάννα Στανελούδη</u> , Συνιδρύτρια & Chief Risk Officer της Finclude
Θεματική Ενότητα: Προκλήσεις & Εμπειρίες Γυναικών στην Καινοτομία – Επιχειρηματικότητα			Δρ. <u>Καλλιόπη Δαλακλειδίδη</u> , Μεταδιδακτορική ερευνήτρια στο Τμήμα Επιστήμης και Τεχνολογίας Τροφίμων, Πανεπιστήμιο Πελοποννήσου, Πρόεδρος του IEEE Greece Section Women in Engineering Affinity Group
10.30 – 10.45	Εισήγηση: 101: Why to do IT κα. Μάγκυ Κοντού, Συνιδρύτρια - Lead Product & UI/UX Designer, SimpleApps		κα. <u>Μάγκυ Κοντού</u> , Συνιδρύτρια - Lead Product & UI/UX Designer, SimpleApps
10.45 – 10.55	Ερωτήσεις & Συζήτηση		Δρ. <u>Ρίβα Λάββα</u> , Επίκ. Καθηγήτρια Σχολής Αρχιτεκτόνων Μηχανικών ΕΜΠ, Πρόεδρος της Επιτροπής Ισότητας Φύλων ΕΜΠ
10.55 – 11.10	Εισήγηση: Η πορεία μου στην Επιχειρηματικότητα. Ο αντίκτυπος του ακαδημαϊκού χώρου κα. Ιωάννα Στανελούδη, Συνιδρύτρια & Chief Risk Officer της Finclude		κα. <u>Ρούλα Μπαγκαλιά</u> , Διευθύντρια & μέλος ΣΕ, egg - enter*grow*go
11.10 – 11.20	Ερωτήσεις & Συζήτηση	13.30 Τέλος της Ημερίδας	
Θεματική Ενότητα: Η Συνεισφορά των Γυναικών στην Καινοτομία – Επιχειρηματικότητα			
11.20 – 11.35	Εισήγηση: Η συμβολή των Γυναικών στην Καινοτομία Επιχειρηματικότητα κα. Ρούλα Μπαχαλιά, Διευθύντρια & μέλος ΣΕ, egg - enter*grow*go		
11.35 – 11.45	Ερωτήσεις & Συζήτηση		
Θεματική Ενότητα: Ενωσιμότητα της Εμφυλής Διάστασης στην Καινοτομία – Επιχειρηματικότητα			
11.45 – 12.00	Εισήγηση: Ο Καινοτόμος Θηλυκός Νους Δρ. Ρίβα Λάββα, Επίκ. Καθηγήτρια Σχολής Αρχιτεκτόνων Μηχανικών ΕΜΠ, Πρόεδρος της Επιτροπής Ισότητας Φύλων ΕΜΠ		
12.00 – 12.10	Ερωτήσεις & Συζήτηση		
12.10-12.30	Διάλειμμα		

Table 26 ECE-NTUA WIN event agenda & panellists

3.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB)

3.6.1 Online awareness session

Introduction

IRB decided to host two awareness sessions and divide the audience in order to be able to organise them on site, instead of online.

1st Awareness session at IRB BARCELONA

Agenda

On 15 October 2021, a session was planned to present the plan to the Equality Commission (internal stakeholders). The structure of the session was the following:

- _____
- Main Factors Taken into consideration in the design of the GEP.
- _____
- Phases of the Project
- _____
- Approval Phase
- _____
- Involvement and creation of working groups
- _____
- Feedback session
- _____
- Evaluation Methodology
- _____
- Next Steps of the project
- _____

Table 27 IRB 1st Awareness session agenda

Participants

In the presentation session, 7 (28% men, 72% women) people participated in the session. These 7 members of the IRB community are part of the Equality Commission, Equality Diversity Committee and CALIPER Working Group.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Minutes

The session was organised in one of the auditoriums of the IRB Barcelona. The session was intended to introduce and explain the Gender Equality Plan, start the creation of working groups, and receive feedback from the involved stakeholders. The Equality Commission is a very important commission inside the Institute, not only for the purpose of being involved in all matters related to equality and diversity, but also for being the direct representation of the IRB Barcelona Work Council in these topics.

The main concern of the members of the Equality Commission is that most of the work done in regards to equality and diversity tasks is always being done by the same group of people, and it's hard to generate engagement and involvement for people outside of this groups.

An overall description of the project and the upcoming phases was explained to the assistants. Initial specific working groups were created to start developing each of the actions in the GEP. In addition the process of the GEP approval was explained.

Supporting material

Presentation slides

Figure 25 IRB 1st awareness session slides

2nd Awareness session at IRB BARCELONA

Agenda

The session took place the 27 of October, 2021. The session was planned to present the GEP to the Institutes faculty. The presentation meeting had the following structure:

Main Factors Taken into consideration in the design of the GEP.

Phases of the Project

GEP 24 Actions

Engagement

Evaluation Methodology

Next Steps of the project

Table 28 IRB 2nd part of the awareness session agenda

Participants

In the presentation session, 39 (64% men, 36% women) people participated in the session. These 39 members of the IRB community are part of the Institutes Faculty, Heads of Facilities, and Heads of Administration Departments.

Minutes

The second session was planned to present the GEP to the Institutes Faculty, Heads of Facilities and Heads of Administration. The session took place the 27 of October of 2021 and it was organised in one of the auditoriums of the IRB Barcelona. The session was intended to introduce and explain the Gender Equality Plan.

Objectives:

- Explain the elaboration background of the new GEP and the importance of an Equality and Diversity institutional document, making emphasis in three main factors: previous GEP, New Legal Framework & Funding Agencies requirements, and the framework of the CALIPER project.
- Explain the main tools used to compile information for the elaboration of the GEP.
- Explain the 24 actions that conform the new GEP.
- Provide an overview of the Evaluation methodology of the project.
- Detect any possible resistances

This session was very important to provide an overview of the importance of having a GEP taking into consideration legal factors, and the framework that the CALIPER project provided in order to assess and execute a gender equality plan. This session was a vital step in order to start the approval phase of the plan. In addition the session provided a platform through which the heads of departments and group leaders could participate and incentive their teams to join efforts in actions related to equality and diversity.

Supporting material

Presentation Slides

Figure 26 IRB 2nd awareness session slides

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Photos

Figure 27 IRB 2nd awareness raising session photos

3.6.2 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

IRB decided to host two internal workshops with the GEP working groups.

1st Internal workshop

Agenda

The meeting was held the 28th of October, 2021. The topics discussed in the meeting were the following:

- Re-insating members to the Working Group
- Presentation of new GEP, next steps and direct implications of the working group.
- Understanding existing mentoring Programs
- Presentation of LGTB related initiatives in the IRB Barcelona

Table 29 1st internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

In the present session 10 (20% men, 80% women) people participated in the session. These 10 members of the IRB community are part of the the Institutes Faculty, Heads of Facilities, and Heads of Administration Departments, and also member of the admin and scientific community.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Minutes

The main idea of the session was to present the new actions of the GEP and to start organising the working groups that will later take over for each of the actions of the plan. The idea of arranging working groups also came with an explanation of the Core group of how the actions were going to be coordinated by the internal project manager and presented first to the core group. In addition the topic of existing mentoring programs was addressed during the meeting.

The session was held online and involve the participation of all the attendees.

During this session new initiatives in regard to mentoring programs were detected and included in the Institutional Governance action: **Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression**. The main idea was to provide a proper road map to all the existence initiatives both in the IRB and in other scientific communities (such as BIST).

Final remarks:

- Working groups will start personal meetings starting in the first Quater of 2021. Every development of the actions will be reported to the members of the Core Group and the Project Manager
- The Equality and Diversity Commission (EDC) will be directly involved in the elaboration of the inclusive language guide and promoting all the new efforts related to equality and diversity.
- Through meetings with other existing committees of the instute (Student council, PhD and postdoct comittees), participation and involvement in each of the diferente actions will be incentivated and promoted.
- More involvement will be requested from PRISMA (member of the R+I HUB) in regard to their initiatives and actions related to the LGBTQI+ collectives.
- Minutes for the present meeting will be shared with all of the participants and signed by the Chair of the EDC.

Supporting material

Presentation slides

Figure 28 IRB 1st internal workshop slides

2nd Internal workshop

Agenda

The meeting was held the 25th of November, 2021. The topics discussed in the meeting were the following:

- | |
|--|
| Final Conformation of the Action working groups and next steps |
| Other initiatives taking place |

Table 30 2nd internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

In the present session 10 (20%men, 80% women) people participated in the session. These 10 members of the IRB community are part of the the Institutes Faculty, Heads of Facilities, and Heads of Administration Departments, and also member of the admin and scientific community.

Minutes

The session was the first session held with the working groups after the plan was officially signed and approved. A final summary of the approval phase was given to the participants also including the first specific data gathered from the assistance of the GEP presentatio held the day before the meeting.

The actions were properly disributed and the working groups arranged and approved in coordination with the CALIPER working group and the chair of the EDC.

Thee session was held online and involve the participation of all the attendees.

The main resistance that was commmented on the meeting was the lack of participation of members of the institute that were not previously involved in a working group, committee or any realated working group realted to diversity and equality.

Final remarks:

- All of the actions were assigned and specific working groups were created for each of the 24 actions of the GEP.
- Reporting template was explained and sent to all of the working groups in order to keep proper track of the action development. This proedure will be done both with the template shared by the project coordinators but also by an internal template devolped to keel better overview of the actions.

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 29 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the IRB events

3.6.3 Public online event

Introduction

Title of the event: Public Online awareness session: GEP Presentation

The presentation/awareness session was planned to present the GEP to the entire IRB Community (open invitation) and the members of the R+I HUB (external stakeholders). The session took place the 24th of November of 2021, and it was organised online.

Agenda

Introduction to the session	Maribel Labrid (Head of Human Resources and Member of the CALIPER core working group)
Commitment of the IRB Barcelona with Equality and Diversity	Margarida Corominas (Managing Director)
Planning and designing the new Gender Equality Plan	Marcelo Mora (Project Manager)
Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan:	Marcelo Mora (Project Manager)
Involvement of the Equality and Diversity Committee	Neus Prats (Core Facility Manager and Member of the CALIPER core working group)
Presentation of round table “Mentoring Programmes to boost equalities”	Neus Prats (Core Facility Manager and Member of the CALIPER core working group)
Round Table: “Mentoring Programmes to boost equalities”	Moderator: Sonia Saborit: Section Head Pre-Award Grants and Member of the CALIPER core working group Louise Schubert: Executive Coach, Mentor and Coach Supervisor Dr. Mónica H. Pérez-Temprano: Junior Group Leader at Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ) Dr. Jelena Urosevic: Senior Scientist, R&D Oncology, Cambridge, Astra Zeneca

Table 31 Agenda of the IRB public event

Participants

In the presentation session, 73 (13% men, 86% women, and 1% non-binary) people participated in the session. Of these 73 attendants are both internal and external stakeholders (70% internal stakeholders and 30% external stakeholders).

Minutes

The session was intended to introduce and explain the Gender Equality Plan to all the IRB community promoting engagement and awareness. With this goal in mind the session had a different structure than other presentation events

Objectives:

- Explain the commitment of the institute with Equality and Diversity and the previous and current efforts made on these topics.
- Explain the elaboration background of the new GEP and the importance of an Equality and Diversity institutional document, making emphasis in three main factors: previous GEP, New Legal Framework & Funding Agencies requirements, and the framework of the CALIPER project.
- Explain the main tools used to compile information for the elaboration of the GEP.
- Explain the 24 actions that conform the new GEP.
- Promote the actions of the GEP by a round table with external experts
- Detect any possible resistances

The event was the formal presentation for the new GEP and provided the perfect platform for both internal and external stakeholders to understand the structure of the CALIPER project, serving as the perfect tool to analyse and design a new GEP. The main objective was to present all the actions and generate the maximum engagement possible with the attendees.

After the session at least 3 external stakeholders reach out to members of the working group expressing interest in at least an specific topics presented in the session.

Supporting material

Promotional posters (English, Catalan, Spanish)

Figure 30 IRB public event promotional material

Agenda

Online Session

The online session was done via "zoom". The structure of the session was the following:

- **Introduction to the session:** Maribel Labrid (Head of Human Resources and Member of the Caliper core working group)
- **Commitment of the IRB Barcelona with Equality and Diversity:** Margarida Corominas(Managing Director)
- **Planning and Designing the new Gender Equality Plan :** Marcelo Mora (Project Manager)
- **Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan:** Marcelo Mora (Project Manager)
- **Involvement of the Equality and Diversity Committee:** Neus Prats (Core Facility Manager and Member of the Caliper core working group)
- **Presentation of round table " Mentoring Programmes to boost equalities" :** Neus Prats (Core Facility Manager and Member of the Caliper core working group)
- Round Table: " Mentoring Programmes to boost equalities" :
 - Moderator:** Sonia Saborit: Section Head Pre-Award Grants and Member of the Caliper core working group
 - Louise Schubert :** Executive Coach, Mentor and Coach Supervisor
 - Dr. Mónica H. Pérez-Temprano:** Junior Group Leader at Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ)
 - Dr. Jelena Urosevic:** Senior Scientist, R&D Oncology, Cambridge, Astra Zeneca

Figure 31 IRB public event agenda

Photos & presentation slides

Figure 32 IRB public event snapshots

3.6.4 Women in Innovation – Win event

Introduction

IRB's win event will take place on the 14th of June, and it will be reported in the next deliverable (D5.6 Engagement activities reporting v2) that will be delivered in M48. In this section, the present report presents the organizational steps taken so far for the organization of this event.

Agenda

The session will take place on the 14th of June at 15:00.

Introduction of the session

Round Table: Women in Innovation

Coffee Break/ Networking space

Workshop: Design thinking with a gender perspective	- Defining the concept of Design thinking
	- Dynamic group sessions
	- Presenting results

Q&A

Conclusion

Table 32 IRB WIN event agenda

Participants

The List of the participants will be included as an annex to this document, the breakdown of the attendance list disaggregated by gender, category, and institution is the following:

Gender: Male / Female / Non-Binary / Do not wish to answer

Affiliation: IRB Barcelona / Members of R + I HUB / Other

Job Position

Minutes

People in charge of each session, exercise, presentation, etc.

Organisation Team: Planning and developing the event

Caliper Working Group:

- Maria Isabel Labrid, Head of the Human Resources Department- IRB Barcelona
- Neus Prats, Core Facility Manager and Chair of Equality Diversity Committee -IRB Barcelona
- Sonia Saborit, Section Head Pre-Award Grants - IRB Barcelona
- Martina Gasull, Lab Manager- IRB Barcelona
- Marcelo Mora, Project Manager- IRB Barcelona
- Maria Jesus Macias, Group Leader - IRB Barcelona

Innovation Team:

- Cristina Horcajada, Head of Innovation Department- IRB Barcelona
- Tiago Oliveira Botelho, Senior Business Development Manager- IRB Barcelona

Communication Department: Dissemination and internal communication

Sara Martorell, Social Media & Alumni Relations Officer- IRB Barcelona

Round Table Participants:

- Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder at SKIN MOLECULE
- Nuria Marti, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat
- Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona
- Eva Vila-Massanas, Founders of WeEqual

Workshop Participants:

- *Eva Vila-Massanas- Consultant, expert in Design Thinking- WeEQUAL*
- *Gema Aguiló Consultant, expert in Design Thinking-WeEQUAL*

Description of the process and structure of the event:

As one of the collaborative actions in the IRB Barcelona Gender Equality Plan the event was planned taking into consideration different points of views and collaboration of various stakeholders. The main organisation and planning was done by the Caliper working group with the collaboration of the Innovation department of the IRB Barcelona. The overall idea and concept for the activity is to highlight the role of women in innovation, analysing different perspectives and points of view of women in different stages of the entrepreneur journey and the factors that contributed to reaching their goals/objectives. The stages that IRB wants to highlight are the following:

First stage: young entrepreneur with recent established startup/spin off

Established: a women with an established company that started as an entrepreneurial effort

Innovation department: understanding and analyzing the role of an innovation department and its role through the entrepreneurial journey.

Innovation regional overview: Having the point of view of someone outside the institute with an overview of the general innovation and entrepreneurial scope from a regional perspective.

With this structure defined, the idea is to have a round table in order to have the participants interact and share their experiences and points of view through their perspective and personal experiences. The round table will serve as an instrument to understand the journey that women have in order to achieve their entrepreneurial efforts and the support and resistance they may face in the evolution of their projects. As a follow up of understanding the path of women in the entrepreneurial journey, the idea was to compliment the event with a workshop that may contribute at some point of this journey. With this in mind the organization team propose the idea of introducing the concept of “design thinking” in innovation and introducing the concept of gender sensitive ideas. To properly develop this topic the organisation team reached out to an external company with the expertise on this topic.

To develop the workshop a company called WeEQUAL was chosen to carry out the activities. WeEqual is a consultancy group the supports the empowerment of women and diversity in the workplace. The workshop was set up to be both instructional and interactive and provide a general overview of the concept to the people that attend the event.

Following the workshop, a coffee break will be set for the people that attend the providing a networking activity to the people in the event.

Supporting material

Email invitation & [Registration link](#)

Dear all,

We are pleased to invite you to the "Women in Innovation Event". This gathering is one of the initiatives based on our new Gender Equality Plan, in which IRB Barcelona understands the importance of creating a vision where **equality, diversity, and inclusion** are valued by the entire community, avoiding bias and stereotypes.

The event aims to showcase women-led innovation by presenting start-ups and spin-offs and examples of gender-sensitive product development.

Information

Date: Tuesday 14 June
Time: 15:00-17:30
Place: Parc Científic de Barcelona. Carrer de Baldiri Reixac, 10 Sala DOLORS ALEU

Event Structure:

Round Table: Women in Innovation

Participants:

- Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder of SKIN MOLECULE
- Nuria Martí, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat
- Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona
- Eva Vila-Massanas, Co-Founder of WeEqual

Coffee Break

Interactive Workshop: "Design Thinking with a Gender Perspective"

If you would like to join us, please register at the following link: [IRB Women in Innovation Event](#).

The workshop will be limited to 50 people. Please indicate in the registration link if you wish to attend. The first 50 people to register will receive an email confirming the invitation to the workshop.

Best regards

IRB Barcelona Caliper Working Group

Tuesday 14 June

Other events

WIN event of CALIPER

Round Table: Women in Innovation
 Interactive Workshop: "Design Thinking with a Gender Perspective"

Speakers:

Sanja Zivanovic, CEO & Founder at SKIN MOLECULE
 Nuria Martí, Director of Innovation and Business Development- Biocat
 Cristina Horcajada, Head of the Innovation Department - IRB Barcelona

15:00h - 17:30h

Monday 27 June

Other events

Tribute to Dr. Joan J. Guinovart, Emeritus Professor at IRB Barcelona

Registration

12:00h / Auditorium room: Antoni Caparrós (PCB)

IRB Barcelona - Women in Innovation Event

[Iniciar sesión en Google para guardar lo que llevas hecho. Más información](#)

Name

Tu respuesta

Instituto/Company/University

Tu respuesta

Email

Tu respuesta

Which part of the event are you attending

Round Table

Workshop (Limited to 50 people)

Both

Gender

Female

Male

Non Binary

I dont wish to answer

[Borrar formulario](#)

Figure 33 IRB WIN event promotional material

3.7 Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI)

3.7.1 Online awareness session & internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

The launching of the GEP was a very important moment as it was the first time UEFISCDI's staff would get in touch with the final version of the GEP and could find out more about the process, about the next steps and what should they expect from this initiative. The event was held hybrid (online and onsite) at UEFISCDI HQ on October 15th 2021. All staff members were present and the event lasted for 1 hour and half. The document was well received as many understood its importance and opportunity to position our institution as a pioneer in this field.

Agenda

Welcome note – Adrian Curaj, General Director UEFISCDI
UEFISCDI – Gender Equality Plan – process, methodology, action proposed, next steps
Q&A session

Table 33 UEFISCDI Online awareness session & internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

In this event, 40 people participated, all members of the UEFISCDI internal staff.

Minutes

Present the measure proposed in the GEP and engage the internal staff of the institution to the GEP activities. The working prepared a comprehensive presentation about the process of developing the GEP, the methodology used, the actions explained in details, the timeframe of implementation, the next steps, the importance of the initiative and ways in which the staff can involve. The meeting started with an welcome note from the General Director emphasising the values of the institution.

The internal staff was very responsive when they understood that the initiative apart from being a transformative measure for the institution can be important for the whole RDI community, as UEFISCDI being the first public institution to develop a GEP can become a role model for other research organisations. The document was well received. Presenting the development of the GEP also a branding action can make the process of accepting the GEP and engaging easier.

Supporting material

Website post

Figure 34 Combined post on the CALIPER website for the UEFISCDI events

3.7.2 Public online event

Introduction

Title of the event: Responsible innovation - The importance of developing a GEP– 15.11.2021. For launching the GEP to the public UEFISCDI organised a new edition of the Innovation Cafe, online. The event was held on 15th of November 2021 and gathered more than 70 participants. <http://ed13.cafeneauadeinovare.ro/> The Innovation Café is a UEFISCDI initiative started in 2013 that aims to create a flexible meeting framework, facilitating the exchange of experience and dialogue between entrepreneurs, investors, innovators and other actors active in the innovative entrepreneurial ecosystem in Romania.

In the 13th edition - Responsible Innovation: the importance of a gender equality plan, which took place online on 15 November, starting at 4.30 pm, UEFISCDI aimed to discuss with the actors of the innovation ecosystem about the benefits of such an approach at the organisational level.

Partner in the European project CALIPER, in 2020, UEFISCDI undertook the elaboration and implementation of a Gender Equality Plan. As of October 2021, the gender equality plan has been finalised, approved and entered the implementation phase. As the first public institution to take such a step, UEFISCDI continues its role as an innovator in the Research-Development-Innovation community and aims to open the discussion on the importance of gender equality in the community.

The event started with a presentation of the GEP held by Marius Mitroi, who coordinated the working group who developed the GEP and was followed by a panel discussions with representatives from innovation ecosystem.

Agenda

Welcome note	Adrian Curaj, General Director UEFISCDI
UEFISCDI – Gender Equality Plan – process, methodology, action proposed, next steps	Marius Mitroi, Head of Innovation Department (working group), UEFISCDI
Panel discussions – the importance of developing a GEP	Monica Stroe, EIGE Giorgiana Vlasceanu – StepFWD (business accelerator dedicated to women) Dragos Tuta – Sustainability Embassy Madalina Marcu – ARC Romania (NGO) Monica Obogeanu – Orange Romania Moderator – Marius Mitroi, UEFISCDI

- Q&A session

Table 34 UEFISCDI public event agenda

Participants

The event attended 70 people. 25 were from UEFISCDI, 17 were from academia, 12 from research institutes and around 10 from business. 6 of them did not declare their sector. There were 49 females and 21 males.

Minutes

Present the measure proposed in the GEP and start a discussion in the RDI community about the importance of developing a GEP

The General Director of UEFISCDI addressed a welcome note followed by a presentation of the GEP by Marius Mitroi, coordinator of the working group that developed the GEP.

During the panel discussions the speakers were invited to talk about their own initiatives that address gender equality.

Final remarks:

- Gender equality is actually an important subject for many but there are few occasions in which it can be addressed
- Neither the ngo sector or the business environment has in place well structured mechanism for assuring gender equality
- Many participants expressed interests in the methodology used for developing the GEP

Gender Equality represents a real issue in the romanian innovation ecosystem and more events like this needed. Developing a kit for other organisations can help them develop their GEPs.

Supporting material

Event recording

https://www.facebook.com/watch/live/?ref=watch_permalink&v=4441470552597057

Agenda

Agenda	
Inovare responsabilă: importanța unui plan de egalitate de gen	
Venue:	online
Zoom link:	https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86585777007?pwd=WUIUbnVoR2Z0T3h4em5aVkkrZEtLUt09
16:30	Welcome note <i>Adrian Curaj</i> , director general UEFISCDI
16:40	Plan de Egalitate de Gen în UEFISCDI <i>Marius Mitroi</i> , UEFISCDI
16:50	Panel de discuții Inovare responsabilă: importanța unui plan de egalitate de gen - presented by CALIPER, supported by MARIE.
17:45	<i>Monica Stroe</i> – SNSPA <i>Giorgiana Vlăsceanu</i> - StepFWD <i>Monica Obogeanu</i> - Orange România <i>Dragoș Tuță</i> - Ambasada Sustenabilității <i>Mădălina Marcu</i> – ARC România Moderator: <i>Marius Mitroi</i> , UEFISCDI
17:45	Sesiune de Q&A
18:00	

Figure 35 UEFISCDI public event agenda

3.7.3 Women in Innovation – WIN event

Introduction

The event was held on 10th of May at Wine Bistro, started at 16:00 and lasted two and a half hours. 50 participants were present at the venue during the event and at the networking cocktail after. The theme of the event was Gender Mainstreaming in Responsible Research and Innovation and they invited speakers with different backgrounds (creative industries, tech companies, science parks, RPOs) to discuss about the intersections between gender equality and responsible innovation.

Agenda

16:00-16:20	<i>Registration & welcome coffee</i>	
16:20-16:30	<i>Welcome speech</i>	Adrian Curaj, Director General UEFISCDI
16:30-16:40	Welcome note	Mihaela Toader, President of the Magurele Science Park
16:40-17:40	Panel discussion	Mihaela Doni, ICECHIM Silvia Floares, Roditor Food Market/Weekend Sessions Andreea Iancu, Magurele Science Park Moderator: Elena Cobianu, GLAMI.ro
17:40-18:00	Sisiune de Q&A	
18:00-18:30	Networking cocktail	

Table 35 UEFISCDI WIN event agenda

Participants

In the WIN event, 43 participants attended, from universities, research institutes, entrepreneurship area and innovation, creative industries, NGOs. 28 of them were females (65%) and 15 were males (25%).

Minutes

Responsible innovation means that science must be closely linked to society and be made for the benefit of society, including a wide range of actors in all processes: researchers, business, civil society, policy makers. Two important components of this concept are gender equality and diversity, as tools that can shape the relationship between science, technology and society. The main way to achieve gender equality in innovation and responsible research is to fight stereotypes, so at the Innovation Café they discussed with the guests of this edition about their perspective on the gender dimension in developed businesses or projects and about the intersections between gender equality and responsible innovation.

Main points:

- Gender equality and responsible innovation are intertwined, and it is important to discover the intersection areas, because they will help us build a stronger innovation ecosystem.
- People need to be open and understand that change happens with every step, with every interaction they have, so it is important to discuss the topic and understand all its facets.
- It is important to look at the issue of gender equality responsibly and with an open heart.
- The fact that stereotypes exist should not scare women.

Speakers' input

A few gender stereotypes you've encountered in your work?

There are attributes, the attribute of sensitivity, for example, to make the person seem less capable, the childcare part is mostly associated with women, the parent responsible for family health and health decisions, according to a study, it is also associated with the woman. Parents must be both there, morally and logistically. Everything falls on the woman because that's how we got used to it and that's how normal it seems to us. In the liberal industries, the marketing agencies, we got used to the girls from marketing, the girls from PR, the ladies from accounting. There are categories of jobs associated with women, we expect those jobs to belong to women. In general we are used to the CEO of a company being a man. At the same time, he is the decision-maker, even if he is not aware of this. However, we have complete freedom. We can access whatever job we want. For example, in the case of a boss, if a man shows up and says he has to take time off to take the child to the clinic, it can be strange. If a woman comes, it looks normal. What I mean is that we have to work on perception. I did not encounter such issues, but we should do more exercises. The questionnaires help. If we ask the right questions, we will get the right answers.

Why do you think the equality and diversity are important in Innovation?

It is important in any field. Diversity means that we can have more ideas at the private table from several angles. In Innovation we often talk about differentiators. Diversity leads to progress and development. Gender equality must be seen in the sense that we add value to the ideas and projects we want to implement. Men tend to take more risks, while women come with in-depth analysis and stability. If the two factors work together then a synergistic result is obtained. It is a matter of representation, risks and differences between the two genders. If we look at the world leaders, how the Romanian parliament looks like, how the board of an important party in Romania looks like, we can see the problem mentioned above. Both the female and male populations internalise some roles. A period will be about positive discrimination and will help us recover some lost years. We have reached a point where both categories of gender are correctly represented in society.

What should we do better? What are we already doing better? What are we not doing well?

What we do well is the fact that we get involved in such initiatives and support the initiatives carried out by other organisations, entities. There are a variety of organisations that develop projects in the area of gender equality. Through these projects we try to support women in technology but also to increase their number in the field. What we don't do well is that we sometimes joke about these things. We can talk more about this and contribute to normalisation. Let's talk more about this topic, both in the formal and informal environment. The more we talk, the more we will help. Women who reach certain leadership positions (rector, dean) can share their experiences to encourage other women. It is good to have this discussion in public spaces. We should aim to have discussions about inclusion. The step must be taken to recognise women within a group of specialists. Girls accept tasks much faster than men. I don't know how it is in other fields, but in the area of creative industries it is. In the institute we had to hire a maid and there were discussions in the council as to why a woman. This is how COR appears. There has been a campaign trying to rebrand and change the term in COR, as a cleaning agent. Men need to be aware when it is not ok what they say. Education must be done in both directions.

The main goal was to open the subject in the RDI community about the intersections between gender equality and responsible innovation. If initially the subject was not well understood by the audience, at the end of the meeting, judging by the Q&A many of the participants were able to correlate the two topics and to understand its important.

Supporting material

WIN event recording

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1f2QsziUuvTHizHUoKjdWFbDkFiXLitdB>

Photos

Figure 36 UEFISCDI WIN event photos

Agenda

Agenda	
Cafeneaua de Inovare, ediția a XV-a – Gender Mainstreaming in Responsible Research and Innovation	
Wine Bistro Vinexpert – Calea Victoriei nr. 155	
16:00-16:20	Registration & Welcome Coffee
16:20 - 16:30	Welcome Speech <i>Adrian Curaj</i> , Director General UEFISCDI
16:30- 16:40	Welcome note <i>Mihaela Toader</i> , Președintă Măgurele Science Park
16:40 - 17:40	Panel de discuții - Intersecții între egalitatea de gen și inovare responsabilă <i>Mihaela Doni</i> - ICECHIM <i>Sivia Flores</i> - Roditor Food Market/ Weekend Sessions <i>Andreea Iancu</i> - Măgurele Science Park Moderator: <i>Elena Cobianu</i> , GLAMI.ro
17:40 - 18:00	Sesiune de Q&A
18:00 - 18:30	Networking cocktail

Figure 37 UEFISCDI WIN event agenda

3.8 Yasar University (YU)

3.8.1 Online awareness session & public online event

Introduction

The aim of the awareness session was to officially launch the GEP and present it to the internal and external stakeholders. The session took place the 26th of November of 2021, as an online event. It was intended to introduce the Gender Equality Plan to all the stakeholders and promote active engagement and awareness. Objectives of the online awareness session were:

- To launch and present the Gender Equality Plan of the YU to internal and external stakeholders
- To present the background process and role of the CALIPER project in the development of the GEP
- To present and explain the GEP action areas,
- To promote development of GEPs in institutions by setting an example
- To raise awareness of the participants regarding importance of the gender equality

Agenda

Time	Title	Speaker
13:00-13:15	Opening and welcome speech	-Assoc.Prof. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, EU Center Director (Project Coordinator) -Prof. Dr. M. Cemali DİNÇER, Rector
13:15-14:15	Gender Equalitarian Transformation Processes and Action Plans in Institutions: What is a Gender Equality Plan (GEP), how is it prepared, what components does it have, how is it implemented? Q & A	-Ece ÖZTAN (PhD), Noti Training & Consulting
14:15-14:30	Developing an Institutional Gender Equality Plan: The Case of Yaşar University	Assoc.Prof. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, EU Center Director
14:30-14:45	Yaşar University Research Center for Women's and Family Studies (YÜKAM)	Prof. Dr. Huriye TOKER, Director of YÜKAM
14:45-15:00	Q & A and Discussion	Moderator: Assoc.Prof. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, EU Center Director

Table 36 YU awareness raising session & public event agenda

Participants

A total of 75 persons participated (65F, 9M, 1NB) the event. 15 participants were employees of the Yaşar University from various departments and positions, and 60 participants were external stakeholders representing the following organisations:

Type of external stakeholder	Stakeholder
Academia & universities (34)	Yaşar University, Hasan Kalyoncu University, Bahçeşehir University, İstanbul Aydın University, İzmir Biomedical and Genome Center, Maltepe University, İstanbul Bilgi University, Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Atatürk University, Ege University, Marmara University, Fenerbahçe University, Ondokuz Mayıs University, Sabancı University, Marmara University, Doğu University, Doğu Akdeniz University, Hacettepe University
Industry (14)	Altın Yunus Resort, Yaşar United Marketing Inc., DYO Paint Industry, Pınar Meat Industry, Seger Inc., Yaşar United Marketing Inc., Optimus Doruk Inc., Pınar Water and Drink Industry, HP Pelzer Pimsa Automotive Inc., Desa Energy Electricity Generation Inc.
Ministries/Government/ Public sector (8)	Bayraklı Municipality, Amasra Municipality, İzmir Metropolitan Municipality, Balçova Public Education Center, Konya Bar Association Zübeyde Hanım Women and Child Rights Center

Civil society organisations (16)	UN International Organization for Migration, İzmir Women's Solidarity Association, İzmir Local Equality Monitoring Platform, Equal Life Assoc., Mersin Bar Association, Konya Bar Association, İzmir Bar Association, İzmir City Council Women's Assembly, International Relations Studies Association, Common Life Development Foundation, Women's Rights Protection Association İzmir Branch, Federation of Soroptimist Clubs of Turkey, New Generation Village Institutes Association
Other/Not Specified (2)	Noti Consulting, BC Consulting

Table 37 YU awareness raising session & public event participant stakeholder type

Minutes

While the session aimed to launch and present Gender Equality Plan of the YU, it also intended to raise the awareness of the participants regarding gender equality in institutions. Therefore, a specific session was dedicated to the introduction of the gender equalitarian transformation processes in institutions.

The participants expressed their satisfaction with the event. Some of the participants from academia indicated their willingness to learn more about the development of the gender equality plans and ways to implement the same processes at their institution. Other stakeholders were also indicated that Yaşar University would set an example for their organisation.

Supporting material

Agenda

YAŞAR ÜNİVERSİTESİ
CALİPER PROJESİ ÇALIŞTAYI:
KURUMLARDA CİNSİYET EŞİTLİĞİNİ
GELİŞTİRMEK
26 Kasım 2021
(Çevrimiçi)

13:00-13:15 Açılış Konuşmaları

- Doç. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, AB Merkezi Müdürü (Proje Koordinatörü)
- Prof. Dr. M. Cemal DİNÇER, Rektör

13:15-14:15 Kurumlarda Cinsiyet Eşitlikçi Dönüşüm Süreçleri ve Eylem Planları

- Cinsiyet Eşitliği Planı (GEP) nedir, nasıl hazırlanır, hangi bileşenleri vardır, nasıl uygulanır? Soru-cevap (Ece ÖZTAN)

14:15-14:30 Kurumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliği Planı Geliştirmek: Yaşar Üniversitesi Örneği

- Doç. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, AB Merkezi Müdürü

14:30-14:45 Yaşar Üniversitesi Kadın ve Aile Çalışmaları Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi (YÜKAM)

- Prof. Dr. Huriye TOKER, YÜKAM Müdürü

14:45-15:00 Soru – Cevap ve Kapanış

Kayıt olmak için: <https://euc.yasar.edu.tr/announcements/caliper26kasim/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Yaşar Üniversitesi CALİPER Projesi Çalıştay:
Kurumlarda Cinsiyet Eşitliğini Geliştirmek
(Çevrimiçi, 26 Kasım 2021)

Çalıştay Programı:

13:00-13:15 Açılış Konuşmaları

- Doç. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, AB Merkezi Müdürü (Proje Koordinatörü)
- Prof. Dr. M. Cemal DİNÇER, Rektör

13:15-14:15 Kurumlarda Cinsiyet Eşitlikçi Dönüşüm Süreçleri ve Eylem Planları

- Cinsiyet Eşitliği Planı (GEP) nedir, nasıl hazırlanır, hangi bileşenleri vardır, nasıl uygulanır? Soru-cevap (Ece ÖZTAN)

14:15-14:30 Kurumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliği Planı Geliştirmek: Yaşar Üniversitesi Örneği

- Doç. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, AB Merkezi Müdürü

14:30-14:45 Yaşar Üniversitesi Kadın ve Aile Çalışmaları Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi (YÜKAM)

- Prof. Dr. Huriye TOKER, YÜKAM Müdürü

14:45-15:00 Soru – Cevap ve Kapanış

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Figure 38 YU awareness raising session & public event agenda (Turkish)

Photos

Figure 39 YU awareness raising session & public event snapshots

Presentation slides

3.8.2 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

On the 15/12/2021 the upcoming activities for the GEP implementation process were discussed and possible barriers and challenges were discussed.

Agenda

Opening Speeches o CALIPER Project: What Have We Done So Far?
Yaşar University Gender Equality Plan
Gender Equality Plan: Next Steps
Gender Equality Plan Implementation Process: Opportunities and Challenges
Q& A & Comments

Table 38 YU internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

The workshop was attended by all members of GEP working group, there were also some of the staff members who were involved in internal assessment process and CALIPER team members (total 23 attendees).

Minutes

The internal workshop with GEP Working group was organised online (zoom) due to covid restrictions. Workshop started with the opening speeches of institutional project coordinator and Vice Rector. Afterwards, the overview of the upcoming GEP tasks were presented and discussed. The session continued with the discussion on the possible barriers and challenges. The workshop started at 15:00 and ended around 16:45 hours.

The GEP WG members and the members from department who will be actively involved in the GEP implementation process overviewed and discussed the GEP actions to be implemented. Possible resistances and barriers and mechanisms/ solutions to overcome were discussed. The WG members and other staff members were eager to contribute to the GEP implementation process.

A roadmap was drawn based on the results of the discussions on GEP implementation process and exiting and possible future barriers. The upcoming GEP actions and related activities were overviewed and agreed upon.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 41 YU internal workshop snapshots

Presentation slides

Figure 42 YU internal workshop slides

3.8.3 Women in Innovation – WIN event

Introduction

The action was the organisation of the WIN Event to raise awareness and attracting more girls to STEM areas and highlight women’s led innovations presenting startups and spin offs. It took place on the 21st of April 2022 at the Yasar University.

Agenda

13:00- 13:30 REGISTRATION

13:30- 14:00 OPENING SPEECHES

- Assoc. Prof. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALİPER Project Coordinator
- Prof. Dr. M. Cemali DİNÇER, Rector
- İdil YİĞİTBAŞI, Yaşar Holding Deputy Chairman of the Board of Directors

14:00-15:30	FIRST SESSION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Kevser Özgen ÖZER, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evren Homan GÖKÇE, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sakine Tuncay TANRIVERDİ, Ege University Faculty of Pharmacy Faculty Members, DERMİS Pharma Founders • Dr. Burcu Karaca UĞURAL, Founder of the B-PREG Komposite, Turkey's Promising Female Entrepreneur Award Winner • Selin KÜÇÜK, Entrepreneur Architect, Founder of the FieldTech Engineering, 4th İstanbul International Invention Fair Best National Invention Award and Gold Medal Winner
15:30-16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00-17:00	SECOND SESSION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We've Always Been There: Women in Science, Prof. Dr. Huriye TOKER, Director of Yaşar University Women and Family Studies Application and Research Center • Q&A Session, Certificate Ceremony and Closing

Table 39 YU WIN event agenda

Participants

In line with the aim of the WIN event the main target group of the event was female high school students from local schools. Four different schools were targeted and contacted. They were asked to promote the event to interested students and each school selected 15 girls and at least one responsible teacher to attend the event. While 3 of the high schools were public one was a private high school. One of them was a Vocational Technical High School.

The participants list was collected before the event and signature lists and certificate of participations were prepared beforehand.

In the end total 65 person was attended the event. 5 teachers & speakers (all female), 48 students (46 Female and 2 Not Specified). The majority of the students was at the age of 15-16 (71%), 0,6% was at the age of 14 and the rest was 17-18 years old.

Minutes

The action reached the results and objectives that were set for the short term. In the short term the main purpose of the action was to increase awareness about STEM careers among female high school students, highlight women's led innovations presenting startups and spin offs, and create strong links among R&I Hub participants.

According to the result of the evaluation activities, these objectives were successfully achieved. Overall, the evaluation of the action was very positive both from the female high school students and the speakers/teachers' side. The participating students rated the event very high and indicated that they would like to take part in similar future events. The participants were also indicated that the event enabled/increased students' knowledge about the place of women in science & innovation, increased knowledge of female students about the importance of receiving education in the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Furthermore, they stated that the event had a positive impact on the participating female students in terms of choosing one of the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) in their future university education.

The sustainability of the WIN event will be ensured by organising the event every year in collaboration with the Public Relations and Marketing Directorate and it will become a permanent event.

Supporting material

Agenda

YASAR
UNİVERSİTESİ

Yaşar Üniversitesi
AB Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi

CALIPER PROJESİ

**İNOVASYONDA
KADIN
ETKİNLİĞİ**

21 NISAN 2022
13:00-17:00
EGE PALAS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134. <https://caliper-projesi.eu> **CALIPER**

YASAR
UNİVERSİTESİ

CALIPER Project
Women in Innovation (WIN) Event

Date: 21 Nisan 2022
Time: 13:00-17:00
Place: Ege Palas Otel

PROGRAM

13:00- 13:30 REGISTRATION

13:30- 14:00 OPENING SPEECHES

- Assoc. Prof. Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER Project Coordinator
- Prof. Dr. M. Cemal DİNÇER, Rector
- İdli YİĞİTBAŞI, Yaşar Holding Deputy Chairman of the Board of Directors

14:00-15:30 FIRST SESSION

- Prof. Dr. Kevsir Özgen ÖZER, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evren Homan GÖKÇE, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sakine Tuncay TANRIVERDİ, Ege University Faculty of Pharmacy Faculty Members, DERMIS Pharma Founders
- Dr. Burcu Karaca UĞURAL, Founder of the B-PREG Composite, Turkey's Promising Female Entrepreneur Award Winner
- Selin KÜÇÜK, Entrepreneur Architect, Founder of the FieldTech Engineering, 4th Istanbul International Invention Fair Best National Invention Award and Gold Medal Winner

15:30-16:00 COFFEE BREAK

16:00-17:00 SECOND SESSION

- We've Always Been There: Women in Science, Prof. Dr. Huriye TOKER, Director of Yaşar University Women and Family Studies Application and Research Center
- Q&A Session, Certificate Ceremony and Closing

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Photos

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

News Coverage

interpress HABER MERKEZİ HAFTADA 6 GÜN YEREL GAZETE İZMİR EKONOMİ Tarih: 26.04.2022 Sayfa: 7 SBCm: 26,56

Kız çocuklarına İLHAM OLDULAR

Başarılı girişimlere imza atıp çok sayıda ödül kazanan kadınlar, İzmir'in farklı liselerinden kız öğrencilerle kendi yolculuklarını paylaşıp "Yeter ki bıkmadan, pes etmeden hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" dediler

Yasar Üniversitesi'nin Avrupa Birliği Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi aracılığıyla Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim kurumsal koordinatörlüğünde yer aldığı Avrupa Birliği Üfuk 2020 Programı kapsamında desteklenen "CALPERE - Cinsiyet Eşitliği için Araştırma ve Yenilikçilik" başlıklı proje kapsamında "İnovasyonda Kadın" etkinliği düzenlendi. Etkinliğe, Yasar Toplumlu Yönetim Kurulu Başkanı Vekili İdil Yiğitbaşı, kuruluştan bir yana kadın etkileşimlerine önem veren bir kurum olduklarını vurgulayan Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim, Dr. Burcu Karaca Uğural ve FiektTech Mühendislik Kurucusu Mimar Selin Köçkü, ise öğrencilerle kariyer yolculuklarında paylaşımlarını ve başarılarını aktardılar. "Hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" mesajı ile öğrencileri motive eden Doç. Dr. Cemal Dinçer, akademik başarıları ve kariyerlerini öğrencilerle paylaştıkları için, klasik olarak beklenen başarıları elde eden kadın öğrencilerle, sosyal, ekonomik ve politik alanlardaki başarılarına her zamanla birlikte kadınların da başarıya ulaşabileceğini vurguladı. Bu etkinliklerde bir yandan kız öğrencilerin bu alanlara ilgiyi göstermeleri, diğer yandan kadınların tarafsız ve adil bir şekilde değerlendirilmesini amaçladıkları belirtildi.

Yararların daha hızlı ivmelenmesini sağlıyor
TBB TEİB Çarşını Etiler Etno Medya Etiler Besen Hilyeleri Odullu büste olmak üzere çeşitli ödülleri kazanan, Demiris Pharma'nın kurucusu Ege Üniversitesi Eczacılık Fakültesi öğretim üyesi Prof. Dr. Keveser Özgen Özer, Doç. Dr. Evren Homam Gökeç ile Doç. Dr. Sakine Tunçay Tanrıverdi, başarıya ulaşılacak kadar çalışıldığını belirttikten sonra, kadınların bu alana adım atmasını teşvik etti. Dişhekimiyat alanında uzmanlaşmış Doç. Dr. Evren Homam Gökeç ve Doç. Dr. Sakine Tunçay Tanrıverdi, başarıya ulaşılacak kadar çalışıldığını belirttikten sonra, kadınların bu alana adım atmasını teşvik etti.

interpress HABER MERKEZİ HAFTADA 6 GÜN YEREL GAZETE İZMİR EKONOMİ Tarih: 26.04.2022 Sayfa: 7 SBCm: 26,56

Kız çocuklarına ilham oldular

Başarılı girişimlere imza atıp çok sayıda ödül kazanan kadınlar, İzmir'in farklı liselerinden kız öğrencilerle kendi yolculuklarını paylaştılar. "Yeter ki bıkmadan, pes etmeden hayallerinizin peşinden gidin" dediler

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'GELECEĞİ KURACAGIZ'
Ağlıca konuşan Yasar Toplumlu Yönetim Kurulu Başkanı Vekili İdil Yiğitbaşı, kuruluştan bir yana kadın etkileşimlerine önem veren bir kurum olduklarını vurguladı. Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim, Dr. Burcu Karaca Uğural ve FiektTech Mühendislik Kurucusu Mimar Selin Köçkü, ise öğrencilerle kariyer yolculuklarında paylaşımlarını ve başarılarını aktardılar. "Hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" mesajı ile öğrencileri motive eden Doç. Dr. Cemal Dinçer, akademik başarıları ve kariyerlerini öğrencilerle paylaştıkları için, klasik olarak beklenen başarıları elde eden kadın öğrencilerle, sosyal, ekonomik ve politik alanlardaki başarılarına her zamanla birlikte kadınların da başarıya ulaşabileceğini vurguladı. Bu etkinliklerde bir yandan kız öğrencilerin bu alanlara ilgiyi göstermeleri, diğer yandan kadınların tarafsız ve adil bir şekilde değerlendirilmesini amaçladıkları belirtildi.

interpress YENİ BAKIŞ HAFTADA 6 GÜN YEREL GAZETE İZMİR EKONOMİ Tarih: 26.04.2022 Sayfa: 7 SBCm: 26,56

Hayallerinizin peşinden gidin

Yasar Üniversitesi'nin Avrupa Birliği Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi aracılığıyla Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim kurumsal koordinatörlüğünde yer aldığı Avrupa Birliği Üfuk 2020 Programı kapsamında desteklenen "CALPERE - Cinsiyet Eşitliği için Araştırma ve Yenilikçilik" başlıklı proje kapsamında "İnovasyonda Kadın" etkinliği düzenlendi. Etkinliğe, Yasar Toplumlu Yönetim Kurulu Başkanı Vekili İdil Yiğitbaşı, kuruluştan bir yana kadın etkileşimlerine önem veren bir kurum olduklarını vurgulayan Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim, Dr. Burcu Karaca Uğural ve FiektTech Mühendislik Kurucusu Mimar Selin Köçkü, ise öğrencilerle kariyer yolculuklarında paylaşımlarını ve başarılarını aktardılar. "Hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" mesajı ile öğrencileri motive eden Doç. Dr. Cemal Dinçer, akademik başarıları ve kariyerlerini öğrencilerle paylaştıkları için, klasik olarak beklenen başarıları elde eden kadın öğrencilerle, sosyal, ekonomik ve politik alanlardaki başarılarına her zamanla birlikte kadınların da başarıya ulaşabileceğini vurguladı. Bu etkinliklerde bir yandan kız öğrencilerin bu alanlara ilgiyi göstermeleri, diğer yandan kadınların tarafsız ve adil bir şekilde değerlendirilmesini amaçladıkları belirtildi.

interpress İZGAZETE HAFTADA 6 GÜN YEREL GAZETE İZMİR SİYASİ Tarih: 26.04.2022 Sayfa: 6 SBCm: 21,85

Kız çocuklarına ilham oldular

Yasar Üniversitesi'nin Avrupa Birliği (AB) Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi aracılığıyla Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim kurumsal koordinatörlüğünde yer aldığı Avrupa Birliği Üfuk 2020 Programı çerçevesinde "İnovasyonda Kadın" etkinliği düzenlendi. Etkinliğe, Yasar Toplumlu Yönetim Kurulu Başkanı Vekili İdil Yiğitbaşı, kuruluştan bir yana kadın etkileşimlerine önem veren bir kurum olduklarını vurgulayan Doç. Dr. Gökay Özzerim, Dr. Burcu Karaca Uğural ve FiektTech Mühendislik Kurucusu Mimar Selin Köçkü, ise öğrencilerle kariyer yolculuklarında paylaşımlarını ve başarılarını aktardılar. "Hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" mesajı ile öğrencileri motive eden Doç. Dr. Cemal Dinçer, akademik başarıları ve kariyerlerini öğrencilerle paylaştıkları için, klasik olarak beklenen başarıları elde eden kadın öğrencilerle, sosyal, ekonomik ve politik alanlardaki başarılarına her zamanla birlikte kadınların da başarıya ulaşabileceğini vurguladı. Bu etkinliklerde bir yandan kız öğrencilerin bu alanlara ilgiyi göstermeleri, diğer yandan kadınların tarafsız ve adil bir şekilde değerlendirilmesini amaçladıkları belirtildi.

interpress HABER MERKEZİ HAFTADA 6 GÜN YEREL GAZETE İZMİR EKONOMİ Tarih: 26.04.2022 Sayfa: 7 SBCm: 26,56

KIZ ÇOCUKLARINA İLHAM OLDULAR

Başarılı girişimlere imza atıp çok sayıda ödül kazanan kadınlar, İzmir'in farklı liselerinden kız öğrencilerle kendi yolculuklarını paylaştılar. "Yeter ki bıkmadan, pes etmeden hayallerinizin peşinden gidin. Başaramayacağınız bir şey yok" dediler.

YARALARIN DAHA HIZLI İVİLEMESİNİ SAĞLIYOR
TBB TEİB Çarşını Etiler Etno Medya Etiler Besen Hilyeleri Odullu büste olmak üzere çeşitli ödülleri kazanan, Demiris Pharma'nın kurucusu Ege Üniversitesi Eczacılık Fakültesi öğretim üyesi Prof. Dr. Keveser Özgen Özer, Doç. Dr. Evren Homam Gökeç ile Doç. Dr. Sakine Tunçay Tanrıverdi, başarıya ulaşılacak kadar çalışıldığını belirttikten sonra, kadınların bu alana adım atmasını teşvik etti.

WIN event recording

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/14u-TlrrX2W07cwYzvgosJG2coj5FJQbB/view?usp=sharing>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation Programme under grant agreement no 873134.

3.9 University of Salento (UNILE)

3.9.1 Public online event

Introduction

At the National Conference of the Equality Bodies of the Italian Universities, which was held at the University of Salento on **November 11-12, 2021**, the forthcoming approval of the GEP was announced.

Thanks to the network of contacts engaged by the Equal Opportunities Delegate of the University of Salento, it was possible to organise this event at our University, which involves the Equality Bodies of Italian Universities every year to discuss cross-cutting issues and share common objectives and strategies.

Agenda

11/11/2022 (Day 1)

8:45	Registration
9:00-9:45	Welcome
9:45-11:45	1 st session “Lavoro Agile”
11:45-16:30	2 nd session “Gender Equality Plan”
16:45-17:45	3 rd session “Gender Equality Plan”
17:45-19:30	4 th session “Experiences of change in University: agile work and GEP”

12/11/2021 (Day 2)

8:45	Doors open
9:00-9:45	Keynote speaker: Lorenzo ZOPPOLI - Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II
9:45-10:30	«Gender equality from Research to Action»
10:45-11:15	Results of the investigations conducted by the Conference and proposals of work
11:15-12:45	Round table “Gender Equality Plans and smart working: which ones changes for organizational well-being in universities?”
12:45-14:30	National Conference motion approved
14:30-16:30	Annual Assembly of the National Conference

Table 40 UNILE Public online event (2 days)

Participants

The participants in the Annual Conference of the Equality Bodies of the Universities were 148 (134 female and 14 male).

Minutes

Announcing the GEP on this occasion meant that the University of Salento drew the attention of the entire academic community to this important milestone, with the aim of raising awareness of the institutional and cultural implications of the objectives in the field among the internal bodies responsible for approving and implementing the GEP. Thanks to this event, the University of Salento **involved also external audience and part of the R&I hub**.

Presentations, open discussion and round table were organised on the topic of the conference which was: “Gender equality plans and smart working”. Different experiences and programs were presented, compared and discussed.

Most of the GEP already in place in public sectors, government, and research institutions were composed of actions and outcome similar to the one envisaged for our plan.

Supporting material

Agenda

GENDER EQUALITY PLANS E SMART WORKING

QUALI CAMBIAMENTI PER IL BENESSERE ORGANIZZATIVO NELLE UNIVERSITÀ?

Università del Salento 11-12 Novembre 2021
 Convegno Annuale della Conferenza Nazionale degli Organismi di Parità delle Università Italiane

GIOVEDÌ 11 NOVEMBRE 2021

SESSIONE DEL MATTINO

- 8:45 Registrazione partecipanti
- 9:00 Saluti istituzionali
- 9:45 **Prima Sessione «Lavoro Agile»**
- 11:15 coffee break
- 11:30 «Passioni positive. In ricordo di Donatella Grasso» già presidente CPD dell'Università del Salento
- 11:45 **Seconda Sessione «Gender Equality Plan»** (prima parte)
- 13:00 pausa pranzo

SESSIONE DEL POMERIGGIO

- 14:15 Keynote speaker: Sara AGUIRRE - Università Libre de Bruxelles
- 15:00 **Tavola Rotonda «Il ruolo delle Università per la rinascita del Mezzogiorno»**
- 16:30 coffee Break
- 16:45 **Terza Sessione «Gender Equality Plan»** (seconda parte)
- 17:45 **Quarta sessione «Esperienze di cambiamento nelle Università: lavoro agile e GEP»**
- 18:45 Le iniziative UE delle Università Europee, verso un'alleanza italiana sui temi EDI
- 19:30 Chiusura dei lavori

VENERDÌ 12 NOVEMBRE

SESSIONE DEL MATTINO

- 8:45 Apertura dei lavori
- 9:00 Keynote speaker: Lorenzo ZOPPOLI - Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II
- 9:45 «Gender equality from Research to Action» Lina GÁLVEZ MUNOZ, vicepresidente del Comitato ITRE (Industria, Ricerca ed Energia) del Parlamento Europeo, componente della Commissione FEMM (Diritti delle donne ed equità di genere) e del Panel per il Futuro della Scienza e della Tecnologia (STOA)
- 10:30 coffee break
- 10:45 Esiti delle indagini condotte dalla Conferenza e proposte di lavoro
- 11:15 **Tavola Rotonda «Gender Equality Plans e smart working: quali cambiamenti per il benessere organizzativo nelle università?»**
- 12:45 Approvazione mozione della Conferenza Nazionale

SESSIONE DEL POMERIGGIO

- 14:30 - 16:30 Assemblea annuale della Conferenza Nazionale

Il convegno si terrà, in modalità mista, nelle aule dello Studentum 2000, viale San Nicola angolo via di Valesio, Lecce.

Con il patrocinio di
 Università del Salento, CRUI, CODAU, CUN, ANVUR

Figure 43 UNILE GEPs & Smart working event agenda

Photos

Figure 44 Photos from the Gender Equality Plans & Smart working conference

3.9.2 Online awareness session

Introduction

UNILE organised two online awareness sessions:

- **30 November 2021:** meeting with the Rector and the General Director to share the draft GEP
- **21 December 2021:** meeting with the General Director to fix output and outcomes of the GEP's actions

Agenda

- Presentation of the GEP structure to the Rector and the General Director and discussion about the specific actions, and the compatibility with the internal UniSalento Regulation and resources.

Participants

The participants of these two sessions were the UniSalento Governance

30/11/2021: 7 people – 5 females and 2 males

21/12/2021: 8 people – 6 females and 2 males

Minutes

The scope was **to engage the internal staff of the institution to the GEP activities**. The purpose of the session, which actually consisted of several meetings, was especially to work together with the Institutional Bodies (Rector and Director General) on the revision of the draft GEP, in order to outline the implementation methods and the resources allocated for this purpose and obtain the Senate's approval of the final version. The methodology adopted was to work on a shared version, setting up working meetings to discuss the aspects highlighted.

The final version of the GEP effectively absorbed all the measures proposed by the CALIPER working group and also provided for specific bodies responsible for implementing the various measures and the establishment of a cross-cutting working group.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 45 Photos from the GEP presentation in UNILE

Recording of the event

<https://radionorba.it/unisalento-presentato-un-piano-per-luguaglianza-di-genere/>

3.9.3 Internal workshop with GEP working group

Introduction

The internal workshop involving the GEP Working group and the EOS group was held on the 27th of January 2022. The EOS group is a group that supports the actions of the GEP working group, that has been formed in the university. The full name is “*Eguali Opportunità uniSalento*” (uniSalento Opportunity for Equality). The participants shared their experience and planned the future actions and activities related to the GEP implementation.

Agenda

- _____ Presentation and discussion about the implemented and ongoing GEP activities
- _____ Discussion about the planned and future actions for further improvement

Table 41 UNILE internal workshop with GEP working group agenda

Participants

The participants of this meeting were the GEP working group and the EOS group. In total 17 people attended, 14 females and 3 males.

Minutes

The need to involve all the components of the University in the implementation of the GEP and the importance of the goal achieved, the approval of the first GEP of Unisalento, has led the Institutional Bodies to consider indispensable a moment of wide-ranging sharing, as an indispensable step to obtain the commitment of the resources in charge to follow with motivation and perseverance the process of implementation of the measures on which they are called upon. On this occasion, GEP Working Group discussed and the EOS group shared the benefits that an appropriate gender policy can bring to the university institution.

The event was face-to-face but it was more of a conference rather than a workshop.

The two groups work well together and are very prepositive and proactive. More people are willing to join.

Supporting material

Photos

Figure 46 UNILE working group on 27th of January 2022

3.9.4 Women in Innovation – WIN event

Introduction

The meeting, that had a virtual place (meet online) in 21th of May 2022, 10:00-13:00, had the aim of proposing excellent researchers (Viviana Betti, Loretta del Mercato and Tiziana Metitieri) who deal with innovation and who have won international awards on research projects and also women entrepreneurs who work by promoting a gender policy within their actions (Giovanna Foglia, Gianna Avellis and Anna Carmassi).

Agenda

Institutional Welcome	Prof.ssa Annamaria Cherubini, Delegata alle Politiche di Genere Unisalento
Italian Research, in Europe	Viviana Betti, Università di Roma La Sapienza, winner of HandMade project ERC https://vivianabetti.site.uniroma1.it/Research
'Women in Innovation and in Open Science'	Tiziana Metitieri, co-founder of ITRN Italian Reproducibility Network Neuropsychologist Ospedale Pediatrico Meyer Firenze IUL https://www.iuline.it/
Nanotechnologies and Precision Medicine: the project ERC – Starting Grant "INTERCELLMED"	Loretta L. del Mercato, senior researcher , Istituto di Nanotecnologia del Cnr (sede di Lecce). http://intercellmed.nanotec.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/scienza-in-rete-merged.pdf
Being a woman entrepreneur and promoting non-profit activities	Giovanna Foglia, imprenditrice e fondatrice del Trust 'Nel nome della Donna'
Barriers in the careers of women in STEM	Gianna Avellis, ItalianRSA Chair, www.italianrsa.org ICoRSA Vice-Chair, www.icorsa.org
The STEAM Project	Anna Carmassi Project Leader of Stemiamoci

Table 42 UNILE WIN event agenda

Participants

A total of 12 participants attended the event, all females.

Minutes

The event was structured as a congress workshop. Each speaker spoke for about 20 minutes presenting slides, except Giovanna Foglia and Anna Carmassi. Viviana Betti's presentation focused on the role of research in cognitive neuroscience and how the results of her ERC project could create an enlarged and structured working group according to a gender policy principle. Furthermore, Viviana Betti's. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134. also highlighted how the new technologies developed in the project can lead to the development of new applications in robotics and neuroprosthetics. The presentation by Tiziana Metitieri instead developed on the narration of the award received on Women and Science at FENS. This award allowed for the publication of a paper on the history of neuroscientists in the early 1900s. She also discussed her role as co-founder of the ITNR network and of open science within the Italian political and academic landscape. Loretta del Mercato presented her research on the development of systems to identify tumor biomarkers and the role of ERC for the development of an enlarged team understood according to a perspective connected to the gender gap. Giovanna Foglia spoke about being the only female entrepreneur who uses her funds for humanitarian purposes, and about the foundation of the Trust. Giovanna Avellis described her foundation on the Italian Research Staff Association and on the aspects connected to the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

removal of computer barriers for female researchers. Anna Carmassi described her role in confindustria and in the stemiamoci network, a network that has had a very high development among the various Italian universities. After each intervention, a broad discussion was possible which highlighted how much work still needs to be done on various aspects to ensure correct work in gender policies.

The event was extremely formative. The conclusions of this meeting certainly combine high research perspectives with high managerial perspectives. what we propose is to start from the data coming out in this meeting to structure future paths connected to innovation for women.

Supporting material

Photos

Event poster

Presentation slides

Barriere nelle carriere delle donne nelle STEM/STEAM
Ricerca con Open University UK e Raccomandazioni del Women20
 Gianna Avellis
 Presidentessa Italian Research Staff Association (ItalianRSA)
 Delegata W20
 21 Maggio 2022

ItalianRSA
 Italian Research Staff Association
 ICORSA
 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF RESEARCH STAFF ASSOCIATIONS
 www.italiansa.org

Premessa - il divario tecnologico e il divario delle competenze digitali

- Impattano le donne in maniera più significativa che sugli uomini, dovuto alla presenza di barriere per le donne e ragazze a intraprendere una carriera nelle STEM.
- Le donne sono sottorappresentate nelle STEM nella maggior parte dei paesi (vedi OECD su come colmare il divario di genere digitale).
- Gli ostacoli identificati dall'OECD, come la mancanza di educazione e formazione così come stereotipi inerenti e norme socio-culturali, riducono la capacità delle donne di beneficiare delle opportunità offerte dalla trasformazione digitale.
- Una ulteriore sfida si verifica dovuta a una iscrizione nei campi STEM e in particolare nelle ICT, che di conseguenza porta ad allargare i divari e a una maggiore disuguaglianza. In generale, approssimativamente solo il 25% di studenti nelle STEM sono donne. Tuttavia, in Computer Science e Ingegneria questa percentuale scende al 19%.

Premessa – digital divide e 4IR

- Con la 4a Rivoluzione Industriale, molti lavori saranno automatizzati, e nuovi posti di lavoro e nuove carriere emergeranno richiedendo maggiore competenza e conoscenza digitale. In aggiunta, le donne saranno maggiormente impattate dai ruoli lavorativi che sono a rischio dovuti alla 4IR, aumentando ulteriormente le disuguaglianze.
- Il divario digitale è composto da un divario di alfabetizzazione informatica nella carenza di abilità tecnologiche di base, che pone un ovvio impedimento a entrambi l'accesso e l'uso dell'ICT e comprensione digitale al di là delle abilità. Anche quando le donne hanno un conveniente accesso a Internet e alle competenze per farne uso, esse devono spesso confrontarsi con: a) una carenza di contenuti online rilevanti alla loro esperienza, contesto e linguaggio e b) un ambiente online ostile e non sicuro, che molto probabilmente le scoraggiano dall'usare certi siti web, servizi o altro.
- La trasformazione digitale gioca un ruolo chiave nella vita di ogni giorno delle persone, che include una effettiva comunicazione attraverso siti web e social media in integrazione con strumenti di AI come le chatbots intelligenti

Research Focus con OU UK

- Comprendere il ruolo di identità (intersezionalità) e di stereotipi per infrangere le culture nascoste in STEM/STEAM che prevengono le opportunità di carriere delle donne.
- L'obiettivo della ricerca è quello di produrre un position paper che adotti delle lenti differenti con cui guardare alle donne nelle STEM e alle barriere.
- Una forte revisione della letteratura per dibattere la complessità e per capire se i dati possono dirci quale ruolo il comprendere le identità e i comportamenti stereotipati possono aiutare nell'abbattere valori della cultura sottostante.

Event recording

https://drive.google.com/file/d/16xcRMCemedc9xn11cLM4aQnZm6ZOPndC/view?usp=sharing_eil_se_dm&ts=628e0219

3.10 Summary of the participants

This summary contains two tables:

1. The overall reach of the activities per partner and per event
2. The overall reach of different stakeholders (approximately)

In the table below, there is an overview of all the events, demonstrating the number of participants in the different events for each RPO/RFO.*

Type of event Partner	Awareness raising sessions	Internal GEP working group workshop	Public event	WIN event	Total
UZG – FER	50	5	50	203	258
SRNSFG	16	9	16	52	77
STU BA	21	97	54	97	172
ULB	66	10	66	93	169
ECE - NTUA	33	9	19	59	120
IRB	46	10	73	-	129
UEFISCDI	40	40	70	43	153
YU	75	23	75	65	163
UNILE	15	17	148	12	192

*Number in orange refer to joint events

Table 43 Overall reach of the activities per partner and per event

In the table below there is an overview of the stakeholder types reached through the activities per partner (approximately).

Type of stakeholder Partner	Internal staff	Academia	Industry	Government/ Ministries	Public sector	Civil society	Students
UZG – FER	65	15	13	3	3	1	158
SRNSFG	51	4	4	-	17	-	-
STU BA	21	105	37	5	-	4	-
ULB	10	36	20	5	3	2	93
ECE - NTUA	77	26	6	1	5	-	-
IRB	90	30	19	-	-	-	-
UEFISCDI	65	54	25	-	-	3	-
YU	48	34	16	8	-	16	48
UNILE	32	160	-	-	-	-	-
Total	459	464	140	22	28	26	299

Table 44 Summary of the types of stakeholder attracted by the RPOs/RFOs

4 Conclusion and next steps

The present deliverable reports the engagement activities that took place in the context of T5.3, T5.2 and T6.2 by each of the GEP implementing partners. In particular, the CALIPER partners organised four different type of events (either standalone or merged some of the sessions below):

- The online awareness raising sessions (T5.3)
- The internal GEP working group workshop (T5.3)
- The public event (T6.2)
- The “Woman in Innovation” – WIN event (T5.2)

Through these events, the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs had the opportunity to engage internal and external stakeholders with their GEP actions. Internally the engagement of the internal staff across all managerial levels can enhance the internal gender equality culture and bring institutional change. Externally the engagement of the R&I Hubs that the RPOs/RFOs have created in the context of the project, with stakeholders from the local and national ecosystems are an attempt to influence using the project’s results other academic institutions/organisations, or industry players, to adopt gender equal policies and structure their own GEP.

During the next period the CALIPER partners will organise two more online awareness raising sessions. These activities will be reported in the follow up deliverable *D5.6. Engagement activities reporting v2*, that is foreseen to be delivered in M48.

